

Open Astronomy Schools:

Mission-Oriented Open Schooling

List of participants

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Table of Contents

1. Excellence	3
1.1. Objectives	4
1.2. Relation to the work programme	6
1.3. Concept and methodology; quality of the measures	7
1.3.1. Methodology	10
1.3.2. OpenAstroSchools Gender Dimension	15
2. Impact	16
2.1. Expected impacts	16
2.1.1. Short term impact: 0-2.5 years	16
2.1.2. Medium to long-term impact: 2.5-10 years	20
2.2. Measures to maximise impact	21
2.2.1. Dissemination and exploitation of results	21
2.2.2. Communication activities	22
3. Implementation	26
3.1. Work plan – Work packages and deliverables	26
3.1.1. Overall work Plan	26
3.2. Management structure and procedures	40
3.2.1. Organisation structure and decision-making	40
3.2.2. Milestones	42
3.2.3. Risk mitigation	42
3.3. Consortium as a whole	43
3.4. Resources to be committed	45

1. Excellence

“To transition to the 21st century, schools need to take a risk – they need a moonshot”

– Esther Wojcicki, Moonshots in Education (2014)

Open Schooling is a fundamental shift to give students more autonomy and agency in their local community and entrust them with greater ownership of their learning outcomes. Relevance is key for today’s students, who have the desire and capacity to lead these “moonshots”–ambitious, exploratory and ground-breaking projects based on specific and relevant challenges. The fields of space science and its technologies are excellent launch points for moonshots in science education that emphasize open schooling. Last July, millions of people worldwide celebrated the 50th anniversary of the very first “moonshot”, the Apollo 11 landing on the Moon in 1969¹. Space has great appeal for large sections of the public (Russo & Christensen 2010). The idea of space travel exploits widespread excitement around exploration and adventure, and space images are spectacularly compelling. Space sciences deal with the origins and evolution of the Universe as a whole – topics of broad philosophical interest. The possibility of life in outer space is also deeply embedded in social imagination, especially of young people (Graham, 2002). Finally, space science and technologies encompass a broad range of formal education subjects including biology, geology, chemistry, physics, engineering, philosophy, and history and key skills such as creativity, collaboration across sectors and project management (Pompea & Russo 2019).

Space science and technologies have a large impact on the daily lives of European citizens in a wide range of areas, including transport, agriculture, weather forecasting, and security. They also play an important role in the implementation of European Union policies, from environmental management, through transport and navigation, to coordinating suitable responses to natural disasters such as wildfires, and as such, the space sciences address key challenges for European-wide and local community well-being².

As highlighted by the Horizon 2020 call: Open Schooling and Collaboration on Science Education, Europe faces a shortfall in science-knowledgeable people at all levels of society. As the European Commission’s Report for Responsible Citizenship (Hazelkorn et al., 2015) points out, the future of European (science) education can be undermined by:

- Wide disparities in participation in science education, in formal, non-formal, and informal settings, across regions, cultures, and gender which are blocking the full involvement in society of all citizens and talents.
- Declining interest in science studies and related careers that are essential to meet the demand for well-prepared graduates (at all levels) and new research and development personnel in the associated fields.
- Insufficient understanding of the wide competencies required by the teachers and teacher educators for enhancing personal and collaborative achievements of their students in STEAM³ areas.
- Inadequate teaching and insufficient family involvement needed to inspire the curiosity of children
- Inability to shift the emphasis from knowing facts to doing innovative and enjoyable things with knowledge, including being creative with the application of ideas.
- Inadequate public knowledge and understanding of the complexities of how science and society interact to meet societal challenges.
- Little involvement of community stakeholders in science education policy, and in how the formal education system supports learning related to research, development and innovation.

Each of these concerns is serious, with significant repercussions if they are not addressed. The Open Astronomy Schools (OpenAstroSchools) project is designed to address these pressing issues and is devoted to the closing of these critical gaps. The project’s aim is to develop and coordinate innovative, transdisciplinary Moonshots: Grand Research and Innovation Open Schooling Challenges and support students, teachers, enterprises and civil society to work together to respond to these challenges through Open Schooling Mission-oriented projects developed and implemented at the local, national and international level. These Open Schooling Mission-oriented projects will motivate and attract the interest of students, family members, young scientists, teachers, and society towards science and science-related careers. Due to their wide appeal to both pupils and the general public, astronomy and space sciences are uniquely suited for this approach, and can serve as the spearhead of wider-ranging STEAM initiatives in the same mold.

Through the Open Schooling Mission-oriented projects, OpenAstroSchools will transform schools into science communication hubs and innovation spaces. Schools will be a reference point for their local communities, contributing towards

¹ PI-IAU coordinated the global celebration MoonLanding50: with reported and over 1 million people directly participating in activities in 128 countries worldwide.. More information: www.moonlanding50.org

² https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/space_en

³ STEAM fields are science, technology, engineering, art and mathematics. STEAM is also an approach to integrate STEM subjects into various relevant education disciplines. These programs aim to teach students innovation, to think critically and use engineering or technology in imaginative designs or creative approaches to real-world problems while building on students’ research and innovation skills

a more scientifically literate and informed society. This will contribute to students' appreciation of science, increasing their science literacy and inspiring them to consider up-taking science careers. With OpenAstroSchools, schools will become incubators of innovative ideas and collaboration platforms between stakeholders, to promote entrepreneurship skills in the early stages of a student's academic career. OpenAstroSchools will also support schools to make use of cutting-edge technology infrastructures such as robotic telescopes and satellites for educational and outreach purposes within the framework of meaningful Mission-oriented projects.

Despite society's increasing dependence upon – and increasing need for – scientific solutions to global, regional, and local challenges, the understanding of the role of science in society remains an underdeveloped area that is often daunting and impenetrable to the public. In this project, the use of student creativity is key to a powerful strategy to effectively communicate scientific information to increase informed-decision making. This approach will also motivate students and young researchers to follow scientific careers.

The OpenAstroSchools consortium brings a unique combination of experience and expertise:

- Demonstrated ability and track record in carrying out the broad range of activities mandated in the Call with high impact;
- Links between space science research at universities, industrial innovators and global space education networks for children and teenagers that are an ideal basis to develop collaborative and meaningful Mission-oriented projects;
- A broad dissemination network within Europe and globally with access to schools, teachers, researchers and innovators– both bottom-up networks and top-down groupings;
- Cost-effectiveness, by exploiting and expanding the infrastructure and resources developed with previous investments by DG Growth in FP7 and H2020 space projects;

1.1. Objectives

The main objectives of the proposed project are the following:

01. Establish OpenAstroSchools based on a Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach

OpenAstroSchools will implement a Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach following the European Union's 'Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union' strategy (Mazzucato, M. (2018) blended with the Open Schooling methodology originally introduced in the H2020 *Open Schools for Open Societies* (OSOS) project⁴. OSOS has already introduced and tested the OSOS Open Schooling methodology in more than 1000 schools in 10 European countries. To achieve this, OpenAstroSchools will develop a Mission-Oriented Open Schooling (see section 1.3.2) approach targeted at schools in partnership with community stakeholders, comprising 3 Phases: Open School Challenges Development – for development, by the OpenAstroSchools Consortium, of the scope and context of the Grand Challenges and respective Missions; Challenges Journey – for submission, by the teams of schools-stakeholders, of the mission-oriented concept notes, and follow-up mentoring on project development; Local Implementation – for local implementation of the selected proposals (the selected proposals will be implemented in schools throughout Europe and beyond, with at least 10 schools per partner country).

02. Support schools in adopting open schooling approaches to tackle societal challenges, based on STEM and community engagement best practices, through collaborations among formal, non-formal, and informal education providers, enterprises, research institutes, policy-makers and civil society

The Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach will be targeted at teams of schools in partnership with community stakeholders, including families, researchers, professionals from industry, enterprises, policy-makers, and civil and wider society. In the first year of the project, OpenAstroSchools will launch the Open Schooling Missions, for which the school-stakeholder proponent teams will be able to submit their concept notes, aimed at tackling these missions through multi-stakeholder collaboration. Each team will select a mission based on the relevance for their local community. OpenAstroSchools has identified 3 preliminary Grand R&I Open Schooling Challenges (Climate Change; Expanding Horizons: Living in the Solar System; Life in the Universe) as well as corresponding Open Schooling Missions (see Table 1.2.). The submitted proposals by the school-stakeholder teams will be reviewed by Mission Boards (see Section 1.3.2), and the selected ones will be supported by an Iteration and Mentorship Programme, which includes a Hackathon, based on STEM and community engagement-best practices, for further development and testing of the proposals.

03. Enhance cooperation across communities worldwide, by involving schools and community stakeholders as active agents in tackling local-to-global relevant societal missions

The Mission Boards will make an initial short selection of 30 proposals per Open Schooling Challenges, which will be implemented locally by the respective teams. From this subset, three proposals per Challenge (9 total) will be selected based on the eligibility criteria set by the Mission Boards, and will be invited to participate in a final Hackathon for further development and scalability of the projects. These projects will be implemented in several school contexts in different countries, and the corresponding tools and resources will be published online – in the OpenAstroSchools Toolkit – and will be available for educators around the world. With this model, schools and community stakeholders from different countries across the world will be able to collaborate in a complementary way towards a broader common goal.

04. Set-up a network of OpenAstroSchools in Europe and beyond, promoting a large-scale awareness-raising mechanism that enhances entrepreneurship, networking expertise, sharing, and applying science and technology research to science learning environments and projects

OpenAstroSchools will take advantage of the unique network of schools brought by the consortium: the IAU Einstein Schools (International Astronomical Union, Leiden University) that brings modern science to the hands of students; the Galileo Schools (NUCLIO) that are developing community-wide activities to improve the competence profile of educators to embrace innovative model to facilitate learning; and the Open Astronomy Schools, a recently established network of schools (supported by the International Astronomical Union) which are aiming to introduce an open schooling culture in their settings. The project team will ensure a fair coverage of urban and rural areas in each country. Moreover, the consortium has a great capacity to promote astronomy and space-related activities in educational settings using its extensive networks (e.g. H2020 OSOS, FP7 Universe Awareness, H2020 Space Awareness, H2020 spaceEU, IAU100 and other large-scale initiatives).

05. Implement advocacy actions towards policy-makers and textbook publishers to develop a legacy and sustainability plan that goes beyond the duration of the project

OpenAstroSchools will develop and implement an advocacy and sustainability strategy for OpenAstroSchools, by engaging with national and European policymakers to highlight the important role of open schooling for research and innovation education, and will also advocate for a wider use of open schooling approaches resources in school textbooks in 8 European countries.

To achieve these objectives the consortium brings together expertise from different fields:

- Global coordination experience for more than 10 years of the coordinator P1-IAU, which has been leading large-scale science education projects, such as the UNESCO/IAU International Year of Astronomy 2009 and the on-going celebrations of the P1-IAU Centenary: IAU100, with a large number of educational activities, like the MoonLanding50 or Einstein Schools.
- Expertise in leading large-scale Open Schooling projects: P3-EA is the coordinator of H2020 Open Schools for Open Societies and P2-ULEI is the coordinator of H2020 Open Science Hub Network.
- Schools – a large networks of schools and formal education experts (represented by all the partners) (over 10 000 schools in Europe and more than 500 outside Europe)
- Non-formal and Informal Science Education Providers and Leaders (represented by Cité de l'espace, Austrian Space Forum, NOA, Trinity College Dublin – Science Gallery, the IAU via its newly established Office of Astronomy for Education, and NUCLIO)
- Enterprises and professional associations in the aerospace field (Austrian Space Forum)
- Space and Astronomy Research (University of Antwerp, Leiden University, Trinity College Dublin, National Observatory of Athens)
- Space Business Incubators (Austrian Space Forum, NUCLIO)
- Educational Training Centres (NUCLIO, Leiden University, Ellinogermaniki Agogi, UC Leuven Limburg)

1.2. Relation to the work programme

The OpenAstroSchools merges two important fields of research, namely the space sciences (including space exploration and the remote sensing of Earth) and astrophysics. It gathers a large body of expertise in the field of innovation in education and especially innovative pedagogical methodologies where teachers facilitate student's learning. It embodies a large network of schools, and via its outreach and education project, can create a significant legacy in the promotion of science education for all citizens. Transforming schools into knowledge hubs of their communities by involving students in entrepreneurship experiences, with the support of research facilities and members of their communities, is at the heart of OpenAstroSchools. This can only be achieved with a close collaboration between formal, non-formal, and informal science education providers, enterprises, and civil society. A series of activities will be necessary and community actions to integrate the value of students' research for the well-being of their members. This vision will ensure the integration of the concept of open schooling in science education and act as a catalyst for interest and support coming from different interest areas within the school and local communities. Schools become an agent of community well-being by facilitating the collaboration of students with companies in space-related areas, by collaborations with stakeholders in their communities creating a makerspace in their schools, and with the support of its own members foster the creation of solutions to existing community problems. Experts from the community will support students by sharing their knowledge in order to improve the problem solving and creativity competencies of students. The open schooling model will be integrated in the community by inviting families to become real partners in school life and activities. It will be the starting point of collaboration between schools, parents, universities and research centres, enterprises, local civil authorities and organizations, science centres, and other stakeholders. Through the engagement of all these actors in a number of activities, designed to be implemented in formal, non-formal and informal settings, starting from astronomy and the space sciences and extending all the way to the use of related technological achievements in everyday life and their contributions to our well-being, the project will bring real-life projects to the science classroom while also leading the way towards a more scientifically interested and literate society. While designing and implementing activities, the project team will take into account gender, socio-economic and geographical differences among schools and communities and ensure that each activity is tailored to the needs of each community.

OpenAstroSchools relates to the "Open schooling and collaboration on science education" topic of the H2020 Science with and for Society work programme as it aims to foster the creation of new partnerships in local communities by establishing a strong collaboration between science education providers, enterprises and local communities as to improve science education for all citizens through engaging topics related to astronomy and space sciences, in particular how these areas are relevant to our daily lives, such as GPS and Earth Observations. Given their wide appeal both to pupils and to general audiences (as shown by studies of student interests such as "Relevance of Science Education" (ROSE) (Sjøberg & Schreiner, 2010), astronomy and space sciences are in a unique position to "open up" the way for engagement with STEAM subjects in general. These partnerships will foster expertise, networking, sharing and applying science and technology research findings across different enterprises, in particular in the field of space and its applications at a national and international level within formal, non-formal, and informal settings. A relevant example is the "AI Moonshot Challenge"⁵ that invites students, start-ups, research centres, universities from anywhere around the world to submit their ideas to detect, locate and monitor maritime waste on a planetary scale, by combining Artificial Intelligence (AI) and emerging space technologies. The participating teams will have access to AI resources to test their ideas, and after several rounds of competition, a winning solution will be selected.

The key challenges that OpenAstroSchools addresses are those identified by the call: increasing shortfall of scientifically literate citizens, the decline in the number of young people pursuing scientific careers and the decreasing numbers of people who have an understanding of how scientific and technological advancement contribute to our societies. We will foster an appreciation of how the thoughtful uses of science and technology can offer solutions to a large number of problems including health care, environmental protection, transportation, and many more (Rosenberg et al. 2014). OpenAstroSchools focuses mainly on astronomy and the space sciences as they represent important, cutting-edge fields of science and technology, which provide significant economic benefits and can also serve to stimulate the imagination of students, motivating them to seek out science – and technology-related careers. Astronomy and space sciences not only seek to answer fundamental questions about our Earth, solar system, and universe, but they also drive innovation and technological advances in robotics, miniaturization, optics and photonics, high-speed computing, and system modelling, for example. Since ancient times, astronomy has played a fundamental role in the daily lives of diverse people worldwide through its value in marking agricultural periods for planting and harvesting, and for time keeping in general. Today, many technological developments, applications, and advancements have come from the space sciences sector. Most citizens don't associate advances (see figure 1.1) like GPS navigation and MRI scanning with the space industry, but they certainly do appreciate the great importance of these innovations for our daily lives. Current activities, such as the Copernicus programme and Sentinel missions, play a significant role in tackling global problems like climate change or providing efficient monitoring systems for natural hazards. In addition, building an awareness of the idea that we are all under the same sky, astronomy and the space sciences can play a pivotal role in communicating the idea of global citizenship and in bringing people from different cultures together and giving them the opportunity to communicate and talk about their cultures and traditions. This dialogue can lead to improving students' fundamental values-based outlook including tolerance, solidarity, and similar fundamental values on which societies are based.

An example activity of the OpenAstroSchools project is the Dark Skies Rangers Global Initiative (Walker, 2015), an awareness program aimed at students of all ages to stimulate them to make an audit of light pollution in their school/district. Young light pollution fighters evaluate the level of light pollution, estimate how much energy is being wasted, and produce a report to be delivered to the local authorities. They are also advised to promote a light pollution awareness campaign to the

⁵ <https://www.moonshotchallenge.ai/>

local community not only about the value of dark skies per se, but examining the effects of excess light on our health and well-being, and on the health of plants and animals. Light pollution is known as a problem for astronomy; it is also a problem for all living beings in its disruption of circadian rhythms. In OpenAstroSchools, we aim to go more in depth in the understanding of the effect of light pollution in fauna, flora and our health. We will involve relevant stakeholders using satellite data from different regions within each involved community, with support from the science community. By working jointly with researchers we can engage students in innovative scientific experiments using both ground and space-based data.

Another relevant example of the importance of including cutting-edge science in schools and the value of the Open Schooling movement to shape innovation for science education are the IAU Einstein Schools (Pompea & Russo 2019b). The original concept of the programme was to promote hands-on experiences related to modern-day science to students across the world. The proposed experiments enabled students to explore gravity and its fascinating mysteries. Students learn about black holes, gravitational lenses and gravitational waves as they explore their effects on stars, galaxies and light.

Through OpenAstroSchools, students will be invited to go one step further and to engage in hands-on research by using cutting edge research infrastructures such as robotic telescopes, and to participate in authentic discoveries – notably of Solar-system bodies such as asteroids – while contributing with scientists in the field. While exploring the different concepts, students will be able to interact with developers of research facilities in this field, learn about the impact on society related to the technological advancements, and also be able to experience and understand the importance of STEM in our lives. The scientist-apprentices will then take their excitement to their community and disseminate their discoveries within their communities promoting a ripple awareness effect related to science and its importance for our future. Technology plays a key role in the project with topics like lasers, optics, high-speed computing, and computer modelling and simulation being integral (Fig 1.1). There is also a strong emphasis on communication between schools, with the possibility of schools joining together to submit ideas and implement projects.

Figure 1.1. Astronomy is a comprehensive discipline encompassing a broad range of formal education subjects including biology, geology, chemistry, physics, engineering, philosophy, and history and also skills such as collaborations and management. This makes space a natural umbrella science to a more holistic education. Adapted from Pompea & Russo (2019a), based on Miley (2012).

1.3. Concept and methodology; quality of the measures

The main concept behind the OpenAstroSchools project is to transform schools into science communication hubs and innovation spaces. Schools will be a reference point for their local communities, contributing towards a more scientifically literate and informed society. This contributes to citizens' ability to make informed decisions and choices, while also raising students' appreciation of science, increasing their science literacy and inspiring them to consider science careers. OpenAstroSchools also aims to transform schools into incubators of innovative ideas and into collaboration platforms between relevant stakeholders to promote entrepreneurship skills in the early stages of a student's academic career. The existing network of partners school-networks (e.g. OSOS, UNAWA, spaceEU, GTTP, Inspiring Science, Belgium Stem-network) to be involved in the project, over 10 000 schools in Europe, will ensure an abundant exchange of ideas and the birth of powerful collaborative projects as well as a rich geographical and cultural distribution. The project team will set up Space Incubators and Innovators hub in specific sites and will make available to them the necessary tools, support the establishment of the relevant partnerships, and implement the methodology that will allow productive collaboration with

local, national and international stakeholders (e.g., research centres and universities, space business incubators, industry). Families and members of the community at large will also be invited to actively participate in the various investigations proposed by the space explorers in each school. These actions will be accompanied by awareness and dissemination campaigns. The Sustainable Development Goals will also be explored throughout the project, in particular those related to the quality in education, life on land, environment and gender equality (see Section 2. Impact).

The consortium team has extensive experience and expertise in designing and implementing astronomy and space activities that follow innovative student-centred learning methodologies and cutting-edge technologies in formal, non-formal and informal contexts. Our team includes a mix of research institutions (Leiden University, University of Antwerpen, National Observatory of Greece, Trinity College Dublin), science communication institutes (Cit de l'espace, Austrian Space Forum, National Observatory of Greece), Educational Training Centres (NUCLIO, Leiden University, Ellinogermaniki Agogi, UC Leuven Limburg) and organizations with large networks of schools (NUCLIO, Ellinogermaniki Agogi, UC Leuven Limburg) that are already implementing innovative activities in schools at large scale. The methodology and approach followed by the project is based on practices that project partners have extensive experience with, and which have already proven their impact and added value worldwide. The project runs in parallel with the efforts of the International Astronomical Union to foster the application of suitable evaluation methods for activities and resources in astronomy education. Through the inclusion of the IAU, and its newly established Office of Astronomy for Education, we will ensure compliance of project evaluation with the emerging community consensus, and in turn aim to give valuable input to the community process.

Indicatively, we mention some of the projects and initiatives our consortium members are/have been part of, and on which will be the starting point for building the OpenAstroSchools methodology and related materials:

Table 1.1. Relevant projects and initiatives of which OAstroSchools partners are/have been part of

Project	Description	Relevance for OpenAstroSchools
H2020 Open Schools for Open Societies (OSOS) https://www.openschools.eu/	OSOS provides innovative ways to explore the world: not simply to automate processes but to inspire, to engage and to connect. It supports the development of innovative and creative projects and other educational activities. It transforms schools to innovative ecosystems that act as shared sites of science learning in which leaders, teachers, students and the local community cooperate. (Partners involved: P3-EA (project coordinator), P8-NUCLIO)	OpenAstroSchools will use the OSOS Open Schooling methodology as a starting point to develop the Mission-oriented Open schooling approach. Additionally, it will use the network of OSOS schools (familiar with the Open Schooling concept) to engage them in the creation and implementation of Mission-based projects.
H2020 Open Science Hub Network (OSHub.net)	OSHub Network is a network of Open Schooling Hubs contributes to the development, innovation and well-being of underserved communities close to geographical and social borders, by creating community hubs for open collaboration, where schools and communities address local relevant challenges, based on multi-stakeholder collaboration, and have access to resources and tools to develop Inquiry-Based STEAM Education, citizen-science and maker-centred projects. (Partner involved: P2-ULEI (Project coordinator) and P4-TCD.	OSHub will bring in a network of Open Schooling Hubs to ensure that schools in rural areas, areas close to geographical and social borders and underprivileged areas will also be actively involved in the activities of the project .
Open Astronomy Schools Teacher Training Programme (OpenAstroSchools TTP) https://open-astronomy-schools.org	OpenAstroSchools TTP intends to invite teachers and trainers and involve them in a series of challenges and opportunities especially designed for the education community. The project uses the community building approach foreseen in the OSOS (Open Schools for Open Societies) project to involve major stakeholders. (Partners involved: NUCLIO, IAU and Leiden University)	OpenAstroSchools will use training modules of the Program and adapt them for teachers that will engage in mission-projects.
IAU Einstein Schools https://www.einstein-schools.org/	The Einstein Schools Programme helps schools and students across the world to explore the fascinating force of gravity, which acts across the universe. Students can learn about current research on black holes, gravitational lenses, and gravitational waves as they explore the importance of gravity and its effect on stars, galaxies, and light. (Partner Involved: Leiden University, IAU)	OpenAstroSchools will use the materials and mentorship approach from the IAU Einstein Schools in the project.

<p>Space Awareness www.space-awareness.org and spaceEU http://www.space-eu.org/</p>	<p>EU Space Awareness and spaceEU projects aimed to inform children and young adults about current research and issues related to space sciences and the numerous career opportunities offered by space, and to show them that space science can be fun and inspiring. Educators also benefit immensely from the projects by taking advantage of the large array free high-quality resources that are easily adaptable to different disciplines and countries. (Partners involved: Leiden University, EA and NUCLIO)</p>	<p>Space Awareness will offer rich content on space related themes as well as content and know-how for the OpenAstroSchool MOOC</p>
<p>Universe Awareness www.unawe.org</p>	<p>UNAWA is a programme that uses the beauty and grandeur of the Universe to encourage young children, particularly those from an underprivileged background, to have an interest in science and technology and foster their sense of global citizenship from the earliest age. The programme is active in 54 countries. Project funded under FP7. (Partners involved: Leiden University, IAU)</p>	<p>Universe Awareness will offer content on space related themes and input for organizing events focusing especially on rural underprivileged areas.</p>
<p>IAU astroEDU www.iau.org/astroEDU</p>	<p>IAU astroEDU – a project from the International Astronomical Union – is an open-access platform that uses the familiar peer-review workflow of scientific publications, to improve the standards of quality, visibility and accessibility of educational activities. This online platform is a place where educators can discover, review, change, and share astronomy – and space-related activities for primary and secondary education, and also have their activities peer-reviewed by professionals in education and science. (Partners involved: Leiden University, IAU)</p>	<p>IAU astroEDU will offer a series of astronomy and space-related activities for primary and secondary education that could serve as inspiration for teachers and initial input for the missions and mission projects. Through its platform teachers from OpenAstroSchools will also have the opportunity to have the activities they will design peer-reviewed by professionals in education and science.</p>
<p>BEYOND: Building a Centre of Excellence for Earth Observation-based monitoring of Natural Disasters http://beyond-eocenter.eu/</p>	<p>The BEYOND Center of Excellence develops research and provides disaster management services addressing priorities and needs in South Eastern Europe, Mediterranean, N. Africa, Middle East and the Balkans. (Partners involved: P9-NOA)</p>	<p>Demonstrate how state-of-the-art Earth observation data can help communities that are hit by natural disasters, inform authorities on the optimal locations for renewable energy power plants, or help farmers improve their yields.</p>
<p>AHEAD http://ahead.astro.noa.gr/</p>	<p>Integrated Activities in the High Energy Astrophysics Domain: this H2020 Research Infrastructures program provided, among others, public outreach services and material related to research developments in the field of High Energy Astrophysics. A highlight was the production of the planetarium documentary “The Hot and Energetic Universe”, which received the “Golden Star” award in the 2016 international planetarium movie festival in Korea. It has been translated into more than 10 languages and is played in planetaria worldwide. (Partners involved: P9-NOA)</p>	<p>Best practices on scientific writing and appealing storytelling. Mentoring on visualisation of scientific results. Reading strategies to separate key results from details in (scientific) text. Provide material and mentoring for astronomy projects.</p>
<p>Islands Diversity For Science Education https://idiverse.eu/</p>	<p>IDiverSE is focusing on bringing the schools closer to the local communities of rural areas like islands and inspire students to build Science Trails comprised of physical stations that community members can freely access, containing references for relevant issues of the island, promoting community awareness and an increased science knowledge regarding important local topics. (Partners involved: NUCLIO and EA)</p>	<p>Providing a network of rural schools and a methodology on how to engage them in local communities actions. These schools will be offered the opportunity to engage in challenge journeys and collaborate from a distance with stakeholders through the OpenAstroSchools platform.</p>
<p>Dark Skies Rangers (DSR) https://www.globeatnight.org/dsr/</p>	<p>DSR aims to combat the problem of light pollution by raising awareness among the educational community and local authorities to change lighting systems and preserve the night sky. (Partners involved: NUCLIO, EA)</p>	<p>Demonstrate light pollution via educational activities and offer educational resources on the topic.</p>

<p>Galileo Teacher Training Program (GTTP) http://galileoteachers.org</p>	<p>A network of Galileo Ambassadors and Galileo Teachers. These ambassadors train teachers in the effective use and transfer of astronomy education tools and resources into classroom science curricula. The network is established in 100 countries and counts with over 50 000 teachers worldwide. (Partners involved: NUCLIO, IAU)</p>	<p>Make use of the GTTP ambassador scheme to promote the OAS challenges to teachers worldwide.</p>
<p>Global and European Hands-on Universe (GHOU) http://euhou.net http://handsonuniverse.org</p>	<p>A program developed by researchers in the field of astrophysics that developed a series of exercises where students have the opportunity to explore scientific discoveries. Students involved in the project have the opportunity to discover supernovas, extrasolar planets, support scientists to determine the mass of stellar black hole candidates, discover new asteroids, etc. The project counts with the support of several physics nobel prize winners in the field of astrophysics and cosmology. (Partners involved: NUCLIO)</p>	<p>OpenAstronomySchools will use the exercises that the project has been developing for more than 10 years.</p>
<p>Junior Researcher Programme (JRP) https://oewf.org/portfolio/amadee-18/</p>	<p>The Junior Researcher Programme aimed to encourage students to participate in active field research and interest them for STEM related subjects. In the course of the programme, undergraduate and Highschool students had the chance to submit experiments for the AMADEE-18 Mars Simulation in Oman. The students could experience the full lifecycle of an experiment, from the definition of the research question to the data analysis and publication and work side by side with senior researcher. Throughout the AMADEE-18 Mars Simulation, the Austrian Space Forum provided videos, imagery and lectures for selected science centers to increase the awareness of space research and broadcast the vision of Mars explorations. (Partners involved: Austrium Space Forum)</p>	<p>OpenAstronomySchools will use the Mars Simulation activity as part of one of the Open Schooling Challenges.</p>
<p>ESA's ESERO BE</p>	<p>ESERO is the educational network of resource offices of ESA: it aims at reaching primary and secondary schools in the European ESA countries. ESERO focuses on the development of educational material dedicated to space topics. It also organizes professional development courses for teachers in these topics. UC Leuven Limburg is a partner of ESERO Belgium.</p>	<p>OpenAstronomySchools will use the lessons plans and teacher training methodologies that the ESA's ESERO offices have been developing for space education.</p>
<p>Stem netwerk Belgium Stemnetwerk.be</p>	<p>Stemnetwerk.be is a large network of 370 Flemish schools, they form a Professional Learning Community (PLC) where practice and research expertise on STEM didactics can be exchanged. It is an initiative of the Flemish government, Department of Education and Training. UC Leuven Limburg leads this network.</p>	<p>Involve the network in OpenAstroSchools challenges and disseminate specific STEM practices to all OpenAstroSchools as activities to be included in mission-based projects.</p>

The project team builds upon the previously projects and initiatives. It will further develop and refine approaches that have already been tested and proven to work worldwide, and provide a seamless methodology that embraces the ‘Open School’ approach. The approach will be reinforced by embedding it in a concrete training framework with a repertoire of innovative astronomy and space-related outreach activities. Overall, we will ultimately establish a collaborative process between relevant stakeholders in each community, building a more relevant, innovative, and inclusive environment for innovation and decision-making.

1.3.1. Methodology

OpenAstroSchools will be mostly implemented using the Bottom-Up approach, which, in line with the experience of the partners in this proposal (P2-ULEI, P3-EA and P8-NUCLIO – holders of a network of over 10 000 schools in Europe), is the most effective approach to ensure active participation of educators as agents of change. Nonetheless, a Top-Down approach

will also be used to involve policy makers from the very beginning of the project as validators of the overall approach. The involvement of policy makers will also help ensure the sustainability of the project beyond the lifetime of the funding.

OpenAstroSchools proposes a Mission-oriented Open Schooling (Figure 2) approach following the European Union’s ‘Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union’ strategy⁶ blended with the Open Schooling methodology originally introduced in the OSOS project. In OpenAstroSchools, Missions are the mechanisms for orchestrating meaningful activities for schools, while the OSOS Open Schooling approach is the backbone structure for students to tackle the Missions presented to them (Table 1.2).

Figure 1.2. Overview of Open Astro Schools open schooling challenges, with details about the interconnections between the Grand R&I Open Schools Challenges and the Local Open Schooling Mission Projects.

Missions, according to Mazzucato (2018) aim to “provide the means to focus our research, innovation and investments on solving critical problems, while also spurring growth, jobs and resulting in positive spillovers across many sectors”. They lay between grand global challenges (mainly represented through the 17 Sustainable Development Goals) and focused concrete projects. Missions are not expected to be ready-made recipes to achieve objectives and offer solutions, instead they must encourage practitioners to seek multiple solutions using diverse setups and alternative routes towards the objectives set. Projects designed and implemented under a Mission may have different themes and main goals however they are strongly connected and they are complementary to each other, as to their total they aim to serve the same Mission.

Missions are meant to have ambitious objectives, stimulate bottom-up research and innovation, involve multiple sectors including end-users and the public, and have a strong societal relevance. Our five key selection and design criteria expect effective Missions to be:

- Bold, inspirational with wide societal relevance
- Imbued with a clear direction: targeted, measurable and time-bound
- Ambitious but realistic research & innovation actions
- Cross-disciplinary, cross-sectoral and cross-actor innovation
- Allowing for multiple, bottom-up solutions
- Feasible to implement in diverse local contexts by schools and their communities.

The rationale behind Missions: their focus on research and innovation, the involvement of multiple actors and sectors including the public, its cross-disciplinary nature and the direct connection to society and global challenges makes this an ideal strategy for introducing and mainstreaming Open Schooling to schools of primary and secondary education. Adopting this strategy in a school environment is an excellent tool for selecting and designing impactful activities (and clusters of activities) for students. In addition to being introduced to the Open Schooling approach, the Missions strategy can provide the mechanism for embedding higher order objectives and global challenges to students’ work through meaningful pathways and connections and establish a coherent organization scheme for students’ projects. This approach of providing tangible connections between students’ projects, their objectives and topics covered is also an essential element for promoting the

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe-next-research-and-innovation-framework-programme/mission-oriented-policy-horizon-europe_en

cross-disciplinary nature of global challenges. It is a vehicle for getting across to students the message that such global challenges can only be addressed and met through the seamless collaboration between experts from different science disciplines, engineering, technology, societal sectors to name but a few. To further assist the promotion of interdisciplinary learning and cross-disciplinary projects within the school class and in relation to schools' formal curricula, the team will deploy the tools and methodology already used extensively by some project partners that follows the "Big Ideas of Science"⁷⁷ (a set of cross-cutting interdisciplinary set that to their total describe our world) as a means to support interdisciplinary learning (Tsourlidaki et al. 2016).

Additionally, given that projects under one mission are complementary, this strategy also offers schools the opportunity to engage in collaborative learning episodes on multiple levels. Aside from working with various stakeholders and local actors, schools can coordinate their projects and have teams of students from the same school unit or other schools collaborate in a complementary way towards a broader common goal.

Phase I: Open School Challenges Development

For OpenAstroSchools, each Grand R&I Open Schooling Challenge and respective Open Schooling Missions detailed information will be available so the schools can submit relevant ideas. Detailed information and ancillary material will be developed in the Phase I of the project: Open school Challenges Development. For each challenge and mission, OpenAstroSchools will develop: the scope and context for the challenge and respective mission, potential examples and additional resources. Detailed information about participation and evaluation criteria will be available.

Following this Mission-oriented strategy, the OpenAstroSchools project will select a number of space-related grand challenges (Table 1.2) and establish a number of missions under each of them. Schools will uptake these missions and design their own locally relevant projects following the OSOS Open Schooling Approach. OpenAstroSchools has identified 3 preliminary Grand R&I Open Schooling Challenges (Climate Change; Expanding Horizons: Living in the Solar System; Life in the Universe) as well as corresponding Open Schooling Missions and potential examples of Local Open Schooling Mission Projects at the local school level (Table 1.2).

Table 1.2. Overview of the Open Astro Schools open schooling challenges and respective examples of missions.

Grand R&I Open Schooling Challenges	Climate Change (also one of the EU's Challenges)	Expanding Horizons: Living in the Solar System	Life in the Universe
Open Schooling Missions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon Free Communities in Europe by 2030 • Reduce the wildfires by 50% in Europe by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live on Mars by 2050 • Exploit Resources in the Solar System by 2030 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find lifeforms in other celestial bodies of the Solar System by 2050 • Find biosignatures in exoplanets by 2030
Examples of Local Open Schooling Mission Projects (School level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local energy consumption/ light pollution (Dark Sky Rangers) • Schools discover the exciting science and technology behind Earth Observations (EO); learn about satellite optical data basics; Identify different plants according to the different parts of the electromagnetic spectrum; Exercise on Fire monitoring (EObservers for a Safer Planet by NOAA) • Measure, map, visualize and make audible the resonance mechanism of absorption of IR radiation by molecules like CO₂, CH₄ and H₂O. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Living conditions on Mars including (spacesuit and building design for mobility, Communication • Circular ecosystems for production of food on Mars. (connected with ESAs Melissa www.melissafoundation.org) • Prepare for Mars on Earth through analog research and the AMADEE-20 Mars analog Mission. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn how to find exoplanets in space-mission data archives (e.g. Kepler, TESS, GAIA). Showcase the importance of cross-field synergies (e.g. Computer Science) to e.g. optimise exoplanet searches. • Demonstrate the habitability potential of planets in our Solar system and distant stars. • Showcase the technologies (e.g. spectroscopy) that lead to scientific conclusions on the chemical composition and habitability of exoplanets. • Help children appreciate the diversity of lifeforms on Earth as well as the essential constituents of life as we know it. Link to searches for extraterrestrial life in the Solar System (e.g. Mars, Europa) and the hunt for Intelligent Life signatures in distant worlds (e.g. SETI@home). Demonstrate the scientific approach to searches for life outside Earth.

Phase II: Challenges Journey

For Phase II of the project – Phase II: Challenges Journey – teams of schools (students and educators) and local stakeholders will be invited to submit their locally relevant ideas on a digital platform to tackle the Grand R&I Open Schooling Challenges and respective Open Schooling Missions (Figure 1.3 and table 1.3).

Figure 1.3. Stages of Phase II: Challenges Journey

Table 1.3. Timeline of Challenge Journey stages, and number of projects per stage.

Timeline	M6-7	M8	M9-10	M11	M12	M13-M24
Stage	Mission Ideas Submission Deadline for submission: End of M7	Peer-review	Iteration and Mentorship	Final Review by Expert panel Selection by mid M11.	3-day sprint for 3 teams of 3 students (2 European and 1 Non-European).	Phase II: Local Implementation Local implementation in schools and scaling up 9 projects developed
Number of mission projects	Expected number of ideas submitted: 250 per Challenge	Expected number downselected of mission projects: 30 per challenge	Mentorships per challenge: Specific partners will give mentorship to the mission projects		Selected mission projects: 3 per challenge	90 projects will be implemented and around 200 schools will start implementing the 9 selected projects

Challenges Journey Stages

- **Mission-Oriented Concept Project Submission:** In this Phase OpenAstroSchools invites school teams composed by, at least, 4 students (with gender balance), 1 teacher and at least 1 local partner, with diverse backgrounds to share a concept note about their ideas on mission-oriented open schooling projects.
- **Peer-review:** New and existing ideas become better through collaboration, transparent feedback, and iteration. Participants are encouraged to build off of others’ concepts, collaboratively share insights and combine ideas to reach innovative new places. The selection will be done by a Mission Board. At the end of this Phase it is expected to down select the number of projects per challenge to 50 (at least 30% teams from non-European countries).
- **Iteration and Mentorship:** During the Iteration and Mentorship Phase, up to 30 shortlisted ideas per challenge will be invited to further build their proposals and fully flesh out their ideas around the Grand challenge. All shortlisted teams will be guided through unpacking their innovations, testing aspects of their idea, and finding ways to gain feedback from those who might benefit from their solutions. The Mentorship programme will include several modules relevant for the development of the project, e.g. “Community Engagement”, “Maker-centered approaches”, “Citizen Science”, “Gender equity”. This will be done by a group of mentors (online and whenever possible with face-to-face meetings). Following the same approach as the EU’s Mission-oriented policy, three Mission Boards (one per challenge) will be responsible for the mentorship of the mission projects. Each Mission Board will be composed of 5-7 people with a broad mix of experts from innovation, research, policy making, civil society and practitioner organisations, but lead by one of the OpenAstroSchools partners:

- Mission Board Climate Change (P2-ULEI, P3-EA, P6-UC LIMBURG)
- Mission Board Expanding Horizon (P7-OEWF, P5-CITE, P9-NUCLIO)
- Mission Board Life in the Universe (P9-NOA, P1-IAU, P10-UANTWERPEN).

Whenever necessary partners will provide support in 6 local languages: English (P1, P2, P4), French (P5), German (P7), Greek (P2, P9), Portuguese (P8), Dutch (P2 and P10),

- **Final Review:** At the close of the Challenge Journey, shortlisted ideas per challenge will be evaluated against the eligibility criteria set by the Mission Boards. Three projects per challenge will be selected for a final hackathon where the projects will be further developed to be scaled-up to schools around the world.
- **Hackathon:** During the Hackathon, the 9 teams (3 per challenge) selected during the Final Review Phase will further develop their projects through a Design Sprint. Each team will build a scalable realistic prototype for their projects and test that prototype with different school contexts. This hackathon should include reflection on “lessons learned” that can be of benefit to other educators developing their own projects; a detailed guide on how to implement these 9 projects through open schooling will be available to educators around the world – OpenAstroSchools Toolkit. The results will be distributed to all participating schools.

Phase III: Local Implementation

After Phase II, the local implementation “on the ground” will start – Phase III: Local Implementation. The 30 selected ideas per challenge will be implemented locally by the respective teams, while other schools will be invited to implement one (or several) of the 9 projects further developed in the hackathon. Mission Boards will follow the implementation regularly and the digital platform will allow projects to submit status reports and organise knowledge transfer sessions (e.g. webinars by experts).

Based on the OSOS ‘Open Schooling’ approach, the project team will deploy the Design-Thinking methodology originally introduced in the OSOS project to: “promote real life projects based upon the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles: stimulating student’s engagement, unlocking their full potential, sharing results and providing access to scientific achievements and designing innovative actions for all students”. The Design-Thinking methodology, as described in the OSOS project, is divided into 4 steps – FEEL (survey local challenges), IMAGINE (explore possible solutions to address local challenges and develop an action plan), CREATE (implement action plan), and SHARE (share process and project results with school community and stakeholders). By deploying the Design Thinking methodology we will ensure that all missions are tailored to the needs of different types of local communities and that different challenges, are going to be taken into account. To further ensure equity among the various participants, we will also take into account the universal design for learning approach.

OpenAstroSchools will incorporate, as much as possible, in its methodology (specially through mentorships) the value of school activities, after-school and museum programs, the expertise of community science, engineering, mathematics, computer science, and technology professionals, and the experience and expertise of local government and policy professionals. The concept of open schooling in this proposal also relies heavily on creating learning experiences that apply creative problem-solving skills. The Einstein Schools program, as well as the previously mentioned Dark Skies Ranger program, rely on a problem-solving approach familiar to educators as problem-based learning. Students will learn how to address complex problems and how science can contribute to society in formulating possible evidence-based solutions .

With such a problem-based and student-centred learning approach embedded in the Open Schooling concept, there is also a natural affinity and linkage of the project with start-up companies and with other companies that utilize a wide variety of technological skills. Professionals from enterprises and civil and wider society related to the field of space sciences and technology research, will be actively involved in bringing real life projects to the classroom. The combination of real, addressable local problems, student work at school and in out of school settings, experts assisting the students, and local government interest is a powerful model for Open Schools. This combination allows students to directly address problems related to local well-being, addressed appropriately.

To ensure the proper training of all actors, the project team will adopt the existing “Open Astronomy Schools teacher training” programme, update it and extend it to cover the needs of all participating target groups. It will also make use of the facilities and resources available in the GTTP programme and the OSOS project. In addition, in order to facilitate the focus on astronomy and space exploration and ensure that our activities have as high an impact as possible, the project team will deploy and start working based on the resources designed in initiatives like EU Space Awareness, spaceEU, BEY-OND, the tools available in the “Open Astronomy Schools teacher training” programme, and the DSR, GHOU and JRP programmes. Lessons learned, best practice examples and methodological how-to will also be made available to the wider astronomy and general educational community, again meshing with the IAU’s newly established Office of Astronomy for Education, whose mission includes this kind of dissemination. Finally, the project team will utilize all the networks of schools available to project partners through the projects presented above in order to ensure a large-scale implementation of the methodology and activities across Europe and beyond.

1.3.2. OpenAstroSchools Gender Dimension

The Treaty of the European Union aims to eliminate gender inequality and promote equal opportunities for women. In accordance with the Treaty of Amsterdam (1997) and other EU policy reports (EUR 2002/2), as well as the UN Global Goals, establishing equality between men and women is a priority. OpenAstroSchools is committed to incorporating the principles of gender mainstreaming throughout the entire project, giving equal consideration to the different life patterns, needs and interests of male and female participants and project members.

To this end, OpenAstroSchools project will take into account:

- The different needs and responsibilities of men and women regarding care. This includes differences in mobility and balance in paid work and care tasks;
- Unpaid work carried out by women, in particular work carried out in the home. For OpenAstroSchools it is important to emphasise and explicitly recognise the gender gap in terms of unpaid tasks;
- The intersectional nature of gender with other identities, including race, ethnicity, disability, and class;
- The gendered nature of technological innovation: a strong link exists between the attributes of technology (and innovation) and masculine culture. Economic development often prioritises masculine innovation that values growth-oriented profits, while more feminised knowledge and practice targeting equality or community well-being are undervalued. OpenAstroSchools will emphasise and recognise those forms of (social) innovation that are not high-tech but equally important;
- The difference in access to technology and technology-related skills. Important differences still exist in skills and motivation of women in relation to technology use. Where necessary, OpenAstroSchools will offer special training for different users.

OpenAstroSchools will incorporate a gender lens in its methodology, and will consider how groups, procedures and the focus on innovation may limit women's participation. OpenAstroSchools will monitor the representation of genders within the project team and will support consortium members and collaborators with caring-responsibilities by ensuring meetings at family-friendly hours, and facilitating family-friendly working arrangements within all partner organisations. All OpenAstroSchools events and activities will be inclusive and equitable for all genders and orientations and are developed and executed according to gender equity recommendations (using Toolkit from H2020 Hypatia, and examples provided by the IASC Gender Handbook). Gender equity guidelines will be provided to all OpenAstroSchools partners. Gender balance will be considered in all OpenAstroSchools activities and participation in activities, including the composition of the Advisory Board (AB). Special attention will be paid to the tutoring programme to get inspiring and successful role models in contact with students. A dedicated member of the AB will be assigned to monitor the gender dimension of OpenAstroSchools.

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2. Impact

2.1. Expected impacts

OpenAstroSchools will follow a Mission-oriented Open Schooling approach following the European Union's 'Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union' strategy blended with the Open Schooling methodology originally introduced in the OSOS project. By using this approach, OpenAstroSchools will support students, teachers, enterprises and civil society to work together to respond to the Grand Societal Challenges through Open Schooling Mission-oriented projects developed and implemented at the local, national and international level. OpenAstroSchools will develop a pedagogical framework that will assist and support the participating schools in incorporating the Open Schooling approach in their culture through a series of meaningful and innovative step-by-step trainings and mentorship. This will provide schools with the necessary guidelines and tools to develop and implement the Open Schooling Mission-oriented projects in their own communities, by bringing the school in closer contact with the local community, as well as universities, industry enterprises and civil society, and collaborate within a meaningful context of educational and outreach activities that creates local impact, contributing to community development and well-being.

Through the Mission-oriented Open Schooling approach, schools will be innovation and collaboration reference points for their local communities, contributing towards a more scientifically literate and informed society. This will motivate and attract the interest of students, family members, teachers, and society towards science and science-related careers and inspire them to consider taking up science careers.

OpenAstroSchools and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

By considering the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in designing our activities, we actively contribute to the targets set in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development⁸. Of the 17 SDGs, we proactively incorporate at least 4 SDGs directly in our activities:

- *SDG4: Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.* OpenAstroSchools will implement inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities. The project targets educators, young people whose scientific and technical potential are frequently not realised (girls, migrants, and underprivileged youth), parents (disadvantaged families, migrants and ethnic minorities). In this manner, we address targets⁹ 4.1, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, and 4.7 of SDG4 through our activities and outreach to relevant audiences.
- *SDG5: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.* OpenAstroSchools activities will promote role model women in STEM professions, STEM activities for youth, trainings for educators and will address the question of gender equality in science and technology. Our actions are directly relevant for Targets¹⁰ 5.1, 5.5 and 5.B of SDG5.
- *SDG13: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impact.* OpenAstroSchools will emphasise the importance of tackling climate change through activities directed at primary and secondary school, as well as the Challenge: Climate Action. Both relate to target 13.3¹¹ of SDG13¹².
- *SDG16: Promote peaceful and inclusive societies.* By using the enormity of space to give a unique perspective about our planet to children when their value systems are being formed, we shall build and maintain partnerships across countries and cultures and foster a sense of European and world citizenship.
- *SDG17: Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.* Establishment of the various partnerships within OpenAstroSchools will contribute directly to targets 17.6¹³, 17.16 and 17.17.

2.1.1. Short term impact: 0-2.5 years

OpenAstroSchools will promote partnerships and activities between the education community, families, researchers, professionals from industry, and enterprises (namely from the space sector) with the main goal to attract students to STEM subjects and STEM careers and guide them towards studies in STEM fields. On the short term, this will contribute to a society that is more literate, supportive and interested in research and innovation, motivating teachers and students at

⁸ <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld>

⁹ <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg4#targets>

¹⁰ <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg5#targets>

¹¹ Target 13.3 Improve education, awareness-raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning.

¹² <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg13>

¹³ <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg17#targets>

different ages and education levels to engage with research and innovation through a Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach. At the same time, OpenAstroSchools will foster the awareness and interest of students from a variety of backgrounds and increasing the numbers of scientists and researchers in Europe, as outlined by the Call.

School students (General)

Target audience: Students in primary and secondary school (6-18 years old). OpenAstroSchools will dedicate specific approaches and activities targeted at girls and underprivileged youth (see below).

Actions: OpenAstroSchools will achieve maximum impact among school students through a series of direct activities that target young people. Through the development and implementation of mission-oriented projects, students will be engaged in meaningful STEM experiences, based on Grand Challenges and corresponding Missions defined by the European Commission, that will have a direct impact in their communities.

The engagement in these projects will comprise several steps:

- Submission of the mission-oriented concept notes (included in Phase 2 of the project: Challenges Journey): students and teachers will firstly select one of the 3 Grand Challenges (Climate Change, Expanding Horizons: Living in the Solar System, Life in the Universe) and corresponding Open Schooling Mission based on the relevance for their local community, and then develop a STEM-based project proposal – concept note-like –, in collaboration with relevant local stakeholders, aimed at generating local impact, on a globally relevant challenge, through community engagement. Each school-stakeholder team will be composed by a minimum of 4 students (2 girls and 2 boys), 1 teacher and 1 representative from a local stakeholder, and any school from around the world is eligible to submit a proposal. We expect the submission of ~250 projects.
- First-phase selection of the mission-oriented concept notes (included in Phase 2 and 3 of the project: Challenges Journey and Local Implementation): from the initial pool of submitted proposals, 30 proposals from each challenge (90 projects total) will be selected to receive mentoring by Mission Boards (5-7 people with a broad mix of experts from innovation, research, policy-making, civil society and practitioner organisations, but led by one of the OpenAstroSchools partners) to implement their projects locally. It is expected that each project will engage at least 1 school class (~30 students) in their own community.
- Scaling-up of the final proposals (included in Phase 2 and 3 of the project: Challenges Journey and Local Implementation): from the 90 shortlisted projects, 9 projects (3 from each challenge) will be selected to be scaled-up, based on the eligibility criteria set by the Mission Boards, and the OpenAstroSchools Toolkit, with materials for educators, students and school managers, will be produced and published online, in order to facilitate the implementation of these projects locally through an open schooling approach. The selected teams will participate in a hackathon, which will happen by the end of the first year, to share experiences, promote best-practices and networking, further develop and scale-up projects, and lay the ground for the development of the OpenAstroSchools Toolkit. These 9 projects will be tested in several educational contexts, in different countries. OpenAstroSchools will take advantage of the unique network of schools and projects brought by the consortium. Also, OpenAstroSchools will encourage the uptake of these projects by after-school, museum and science center programs. The criteria for project selection will ensure that boys and girls are equally involved in OpenAstroSchools projects and the OpenAstroSchools Toolkit will include training on gender equity.

Impact estimators: At the end of the project (M26), 100 000 students have been reached by OpenAstroSchools, on average 5 000 students through the Open Schooling Mission-oriented Project Development process, and 95 000 via the OpenAstroSchools Toolkit both in schools, as well as in non-formal settings. At least 90% of all students reached by OpenAstroSchools activities will be aware of STEM and space-related careers. OpenAstroSchools will collect data about the participation of students in OpenAstroSchools activities according to the guidelines provided by Work Package 5: Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation.

Female students

Target audience: Female students in primary and secondary school (6-18 years old).

Actions: We address the current and future shortage of skilled workers in high-tech fields by teaching STEM subjects with an interdisciplinary cohesive approach, which will develop the sort of critical thinking skills needed in the high-tech workforce, both now and in the future. In line with the SDGs for 2030, we will devote special attention to encourage girls to take up science, using role models and gender-balanced representations of scientific professions. The various activities are geared to maximise interest and impact amongst the next generation of potential female scientists and engineers. This will be achieved through the composition of the teams and by highlighting female researchers, entrepreneurs and professionals from industry and enterprises in OpenAstroSchools projects and resources. This exposure allows

children to imagine these specific occupations as an option for everyone, removing barriers that discourage children in choosing for STEM. OpenAstroSchools will ensure that children and teens understand that gender distinctions do not limit intellectual freedom so they can chart their own course when it comes to pursuing their interests and dreams. Whenever possible, OpenAstroSchools will establish links with other projects promoting gender balance in the space sector (e.g. Space Girls Space Women project¹⁴). A dedicated module on “Gender equity” will be included in the mentoring program.

Impact estimators: By carefully designing activities that are gender-neutral and provide a positive attitude towards the role of females in space professions, OpenAstroSchools expects to reach around 50 000 female students (50% of the number of students expected to be reached out).

Underprivileged youth

Target audience: Youth from underprivileged communities (i.e. ethnic minorities, migrants and disadvantaged youth).

Actions: OpenAstroSchools aims to advance the educational achievements and STEM-career aspirations of youth from underprivileged communities through meaningful engagement in STEM and a strong foundation in STEM-based literacy and skills. During the divulgation phase of the Open Call for proposal submission, the OpenAstroSchools consortium will make sure to reach out to schools that serve underprivileged communities. Also, during the implementation and scaling-up phase of the 9 final projects, these schools will be invited to test these projects in their own schools and communities.

Educators (Teachers and informal educators)

Target audience: educators (teachers of primary and secondary schools and other relevant education stakeholders)

Actions: The multiplicative effect of targeting educators coupled with their influence on career choices are important tools for enhancing the impact of the project. OpenAstroSchools will engage educators directly through the Mission-oriented Open Schooling Challenges (Phase II and III), which includes proposal development, mentoring program, the hackaton, local implementation of the projects and OpenAstroSchools Toolkit. Also, OpenAstroSchools will produce a MOOC targeted at educators (formal and non-formal) and school managers, aimed at providing the tools to implement Open Schooling and Mission-oriented projects with students. OpenAstroSchools tools and resources engage educators in using STEM to tackle mission-based challenges, with local-to-global impact, through multi-stakeholder collaboration between students, researchers, local enterprises and industry, families, civil society and policy-makers. All OpenAstroSchools resources will be localized, released as open access, and made available on relevant repositories, such as Scientix. These resources will also include training on gender equity. OpenAstroSchools will liaise with European educational textbook publishers to encourage them to use Open Schooling approaches and Mission-oriented resources in their educational material across school subjects. This action will enhance the reach of educational resources and have a large multiplying effect.

The OpenAstroSchools consortium has a track-record of successfully engaging teachers via the H2020 OSOS, spaceEU, EU Space Awareness, the FP7 EU-Universe Awareness and the FP7 Odysseus projects. OpenAstroSchools shall maintain and update the existing Space Awareness repository of open-source peer-reviewed educational materials for educators, IAU astroEDU, that includes a wide range of space topics from the Universe to climate change and navigation. These networks, together with the quality of OpenAstroSchools activities and resources, will guarantee significant impact amongst teachers in several European countries and beyond. The global reach of OpenAstroSchools will be reinforced by disseminating its resources and outputs to the unique network of schools brought by the consortium (250 schools in European countries and 200 schools in EU Associated countries): Einstein Schools, Galileo Schools, Open AstronomySchools and OSOS Schools. Also, OpenAstroSchools will also reach out to other education stakeholders, such as after-school programs, museums and science centers. As a result, good practices and an exchange of knowledge will ensue.

Impact estimators: At the end of the project (M26), 8 500 educators have been reached by OpenAstroSchools, on average 1000 educators through the Mission-oriented Open-Schooling call and mentorship program+hackathon, 5000 via the OpenAstroSchools Toolkit and 2500 through the MOOC, both in schools, as well as in non-formal settings. OpenAstroSchools will collect data about the participation of educators in OpenAstroSchool activities and other relevant information according to the guidelines provided by Work Package 5: Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation.

Community stakeholders: researchers/entrepreneurs/industry professionals/civil society members

Actions: OpenAstroSchools will promote the establishment of partnerships between schools and university researchers, enterprises, industry, local businesses and civil society, in the context of the Mission-oriented Open Schooling projects. By developing projects with global reach and with strong local impact in their communities, students will gain experience with problem-solving for real-life situations and projects, while contributing to raise scientific literacy and awareness. The Mission-oriented Open Schooling projects can take many different formats, range across different scientific areas, and be developed in collaboration with different stakeholder typologies, but they will all share the following criteria:

- address one of the Open Schooling Missions
- to be locally relevant and promote community development, innovation and well-being
- to promote community engagement during the implementation of the project
- to be feasible and scalable to other schools and communities
- to promote gender equity and diversity

In order to achieve a wide range of local impact, with added European value, OpenAstroSchools will strive to select a diversity of projects with different societal goals, for example: research projects, through the development of community-based participatory projects or citizen science projects; entrepreneurship projects that involve local businesses and meaningful responsible actors from the private sector; and social innovation projects, in collaboration with civil society organizations engaged in social inclusion and environmental sustainability.

Impact estimators: OpenAstroSchools will involve around 250 Researchers/entrepreneurs/industry professionals/civil society members from different sectors. 30 partnerships will be established between schools and universities, enterprises, industry, local businesses and civil society. At least 500 local community actors will also be engaged throughout the project. OpenAstroSchools will have a diverse representation and at least 50% of female researchers/entrepreneurs/professionals participating in the projects. OpenAstroSchools will collect data about the participation of universities, enterprises, industry, local businesses and civil society in OpenAstroSchool activities and other relevant information according to the guidelines provided by Work Package 5: Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation.

Families and General public

Target audience: Families including those of diverse and disadvantaged backgrounds and cultures (i.e. ethnic minorities, migrants) and European and global societies.

Actions: OpenAstroSchools will spread awareness to a broad segment of society, by incentivizing and enforcing the involvement and engagement of citizens, namely of families, during the implementation of the mission-oriented projects. Community engagement will not only be a criterion for project selection, but it will also be fostered during the mentoring phase with a module dedicated to “Community Engagement”. Moreover, the open schooling projects will be simultaneously oriented by the challenge-oriented mission and focused on local relevant issues, and as such will ultimately contribute to local development and well-being. The OpenAstroSchools Toolkit that will be produced for the 9 final selected projects (3 per challenge) will be disseminated worldwide, so that any community in the world has the tools to implement it locally. This will also promote the sharing of knowledge and experience between communities and citizens.

Impact estimators: At the end of the project (M26), 50 000 citizens have been reached by OpenAstroSchools.

Policy makers

Target audience: Policy makers on local, regional, national and EU level

Action: OpenAstroSchools will bring additional benefits for local and/or regional government, as it will promote local development and innovation by connecting schools with research and innovation clusters to tackle local relevant challenges through the mission-oriented open schooling projects. An important activity that we shall employ to increase the impact of OpenAstroSchools and ensure long-term sustainability is intensive lobbying activities within National and EU institutions demonstrating the societal relevance of a Mission-oriented Open Schooling approach, both at the local and global levels, by bridging communities across the world in tackling global issues with local relevance. OpenAstroSchools will produce a set of policy briefings on key aspects for OpenAstroSchools, namely on Open Schooling and community development. Policy briefs are the preferred

form of communication of policy actors. These activities will be based on the consortium experience of working with policy-makers (e.g.: Members of the European Parliament) during the H2020 EU Space Awareness, and FP7 EU-UNAWA projects.

Impact estimators: OpenAstroSchools will reach around 200 policy-makers at the local, national and European level.

Media

Target audience: Traditional Media (Journalists) and Social Media (Digital Opinion Leaders)

Action: Whenever possible local and national media will be invited to OpenAstroSchools events and activities, like the local implementation of projects, in collaborations with the local communities. National media will also be invited for the hackathon with the 9 final selected projects. A number of press releases will be issued by all the partners (coordinated by WP4 – Disseminate and Broadening Impacts). OpenAstroSchools will make policy-briefings available on the website, which can serve as background information for journalists. OpenAstroSchools will also target media specialized in children and young people, through the World Summit On Media For Children Foundation, and OpenAstroSchools will promote Space Scoop content to media outlets targeting children.

Impact estimators: Taking into account the media engagement from similar projects we expect to reach around 10 000 people through traditional media. Based on the experience from social media engagement through similar projects in which the consortium has been involved (e.g.: H2020 OSOS or spaceEU) we expect to reach around 250 000 people through social media.

2.1.2. Medium to long-term impact: 2.5-10 years

A mission-oriented strategy provides a massive opportunity to increase the impact of research and innovation, to grasp the public imagination, to foster collaboration amongst multiple actors across different disciplines, and to make real progress on complex challenges that have a real impact on citizen's life. This makes it an ideal strategy for introducing and mainstreaming Open Schooling to schools of primary and secondary education, as it provides a mechanism for embedding higher order objectives and global challenges, which are also locally relevant, through meaningful pathways that promote connections with stakeholders in their communities. This approach is a vehicle for supporting students and teachers as active agents in their communities and getting across the message that such local-to-global challenges can only be addressed and met through the seamless collaboration between experts from different science disciplines, engineering, technology, innovation and societal sectors. By combining this Mission-oriented approach with a pedagogical framework that will assist and support schools incorporating the Open Schooling approach in their culture, and that promotes community engagement toward local development and innovation, OpenAstroSchools will provide students and citizens with the tools and skills to make informed decisions and choices. Ultimately, by supporting schools as collaboration hubs in their own communities, through research and innovation, and by positioning students as innovators and problem-solvers, students will realize the importance and impact of science on society and on citizen's daily life. As such, the Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach of OpenAstroSchools will motivate the interest of students towards science and science-related careers and inspire them to consider taking up science careers. Moreover, the development of an advocacy and sustainability strategy for OpenAstroSchools, by engaging with national and European policymakers and textbook publishers, to highlight the important role of open schooling for research and innovation education, will ensure a wider reach of the OpenAstroSchools strategy both spatially and temporally.

It is expected that some students participating in OpenAstroSchools activities will be selecting their post-secondary school studies and careers related to space within 5 years of the closure of the project. OpenAstroSchools activities will increase participants' awareness of and interest in science careers (namely, space-related). Data will be collected to provide a baseline measurement for such long-term studies and "longitudinal assessments". It is expected that OpenAstroSchools activities will have an **impact on students' career decisions**, contributing towards the ERA objectives of increasing the number of scientists and researchers in Europe, **and specifically increase the number of students that opt for education paths in the fields of science, technology, engineering and mathematics, and in the long term, a science career, namely related to space and innovation.**

The proposed methodology will be used as a reference point from educators, teacher trainers, stakeholders and people working in-formal and non-formal education settings (i.e. science museums) to allow them to introduce the rationale of open schools in their school community through authentic and innovative activities that promote science and celebrate the bond between science and society. Using the OpenAstroSchools methodology, different parties (schools, science museums, local community organizations, universities, etc.) will have a roadmap that will allow them to make contact with open schools and work with them under a common collaboration framework with distinct roles and a clear understanding of each party's part. Our activities and methodology will promote the idea of open schools where students can act as science ambassadors, contribute to raising the local community's awareness on science related matters and making real contributions towards the improvement of the citizens' well-being through their projects. To ensure the effective participation of multiple parties and the establishment of a robust and strong community of practice, the project team aims to achieve the following indicators:

Indicator	Target Value
Minimum number of countries involved	28 (EU) + 20 (outside EU/EU Associated countries)
Minimum number of schools involved	280 (EU) + 200 (outside Europe)
Minimum number of teachers, educators, teacher trainers involved	~ 8 500
Minimum number of students engaged	~ 100 000
Minimum number of citizens engaged	~ 50 000
Minimum number of researchers/entrepreneurs engaged	~ 250
Minimum number of stakeholders, policy makers engaged	~ 200
Minimum number of local community actors engaged	500

Additionally, in order to assess the impact of our project, the team will also deploy a number of qualitative indicators. Indicatively, the project team will use surveys, evaluation reports, interviews (among other tools) to assess the impact by measuring:

- The degree of engagement of different parties (focusing on the open astronomy schools);
- The effective introduction of our methodology in schools;
- School (including Head-teacher, teachers and students) initial and final attitudes towards the open school culture;
- How Citizens view and appreciate science before and after implementation;
- Responsiveness and willingness to participate in open schooling activities of parents, universities and research centres, enterprises, local civil authorities and organizations, science centres and other stakeholders.

2.2. Measures to maximise impact

2.2.1. Dissemination and exploitation of results

The main aim of OpenAstroSchools dissemination is to create value for all identified target groups and to ensure that the OpenAstroSchools project results are exploited to increase the understanding of the role of Open Schooling and building community partnerships (between the school community, universities, research institutes, industry, enterprises, government, civil and wider society) in contributing to a more scientifically interested and literate society and students with a better awareness of and interest in scientific careers, in order to equip citizens and future researchers with the tools and skills to make informed decisions and choices. To achieve this goal, OpenAstroSchools dissemination will share Open Schooling best practices and disseminate the open source material, including all resources and guides. The development and implementation of the detailed exploitation and communication plan (lead by WP4) will ensure widespread dissemination. OpenAstroSchools materials will be available in at least 6 languages. To maximise impact, OpenAstroSchools will exploit a broad range of top-down and bottom-up approaches. OpenAstroSchools results will be disseminated through a variety of existing channels, networks, and repositories targeting (formal, informal and non-formal) education, enterprise, research and governments (at local, regional, national and European level) (see Table 2.4). Consortium partner organisations have leading roles in all of these broader networks. This will enhance the impact of the dissemination (e.g.: P1 – IAU OAE will lead the network of IAU National Astronomy Education Coordinators (NAECs), P2-UL leads science education networks, P2-TCD leads science & art networks). Where possible, dissemination will occur using digital platforms and tools.

Table 2. Examples of dissemination networks which OpenAstroSchools will exploit.

Other Network	Nodes	Relevant purpose of network	Use in OpenAstroSchools	Lead
International Astronomical Union	13671	Individual professional astronomers in 98 countries worldwide.	Disseminate project results and methodology using network of IAU National Astronomy Education Coordinators.	P1-IAU
Ecsite	375	Science centres and museums, science communications professionals.	Disseminate project results at the Ecsite conference (1000 science communications professionals) and through Ecsite Spokes magazine (4000 science communications professionals).	P4 – TCD

Scientix	30	Teachers, researchers and project managers in science education, policy makers.	Disseminate information through the Scientix newsletter, include OpenAstroSchools activities in the Scientix repository of educational resources, participate in Scientix networking events and conferences.	P4-TCD
Universe Awareness	57	Teachers, science educators.	Engage the large network of STEAM educators (in 57 countries) to promote the use of OpenAstroSchools resources and output.	P2-UL
ESERO	10	ESA's European Space Education Resource Office supports the primary and secondary education community in Europe.	The network of ESERO will be used to disseminate and promote the OpenAstroSchools resources and output.	P2-UL
H2020 Europlanet RI	33	Researchers in planetary science.	Leverage network of researchers to promote engagement with OSHubs.	P2-UL
PCST – Public communication of science and technology network	2000	Science communications professionals, researchers, writers, web designers.	The international community of scholars in the communication of science: dissemination of methodologies and results (Sissa staff are members).	P4-TCD
European Physical Society	42	42 physics societies in Europe. Largest network of physicists.	Leverage network of researchers to promote engagement with OSHubs.	P2-UL
European Academies (ALLEA)	59	59 Academies in more than 40 countries. Scientists in diverse scientific fields.	Leverage network of researchers to promote engagement with OSHubs.	P2-UL

Data Management Plan and Exploitation Measures

OpenAstroSchools will generate both quantitative and qualitative data from the participants which will be collected and stored using encrypted digital devices. As Trinity College Dublin leads WP5 (Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation) and WP7 (Ethics), ethical approval for the project will be sought through Trinity's Research Ethics Committee. All data will be collected anonymously and stored according to the European rules on Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 and in compliance with EU General Data Protection Regulation. All data collected will be archived and curated using a standard data management plan that adheres to Trinity College Dublin's policy on good research practice and the European Commission's guidelines on FAIR data management. The data management plans utilised at Trinity College are state-of-the-art and have been designed by the Digital Curation Centre and the University of California Curation Center using the highest ethical standards. Each plan takes into account: type of data; collection/generation methods; verification, access; and preservation. Other data management issues will be handled in the dissemination WP4.

OpenAstroSchools results and datasets will be made available for exploitation through TARA; an open access repository maintained at Trinity College which ensures that all deposited work remains freely accessible online. TARA is a fully-supported flagship initiative of Trinity College Dublin, consequently data curation and preservation costs are absorbed by the university in order to encourage more researchers to host their data in open access repositories.

Intellectual Property Rights Management

All the OpenAstroSchools publications, research, data and products will follow closely the guidelines on open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon 2020 provided by the European Commission. Products and resources will be open source and where relevant produced using a Creative Commons License (Attribution-Non-Commercial-Share Alike 4.0 International). This follows closely the recommendations from the European Commission on Open Education and Open Access. Where possible, we shall also make the source files publicly available in common open repositories.

2.2.2. Communication activities

Communication of OpenAstroSchools activities, events, products and resources will be an integral part of the project, covered by WP4. To maximise impact, OpenAstroSchools will exploit an extremely broad range of top-down and bottom-up approaches in several networks for dissemination of the project, targeting (formal, informal and non-formal) education, enterprises, research and governments (at local, regional, national and European level) (see Table 2.4). The fact that the consortium partner organisations have leading roles in all of these broader networks will enhance the impact of the dissemination.

The OpenAstroSchools communication activities are structured around four elements: vision, strategy, execution and impact assessment. The communications strategy will be developed in detail during the first 6 months of the project. Coordination of this strategy will be ensured by P1-IAU and P2-ULEI through the internal online community (such as Basecamp), and regular monthly online contact with the rest of partners. The strategy will include:

- A comprehensive mapping of all partners channels, including social media;
- The definition of common messages and editorial principles;
- The definition of common materials (printed and digital);
- A timeline reviewed every 6 months based on the key indicators mentioned;
- A checklist of communications activities to be undertaken by each partner.

The OpenAstroSchools digital platform will be based on an innovative open source web framework for the management, distribution and dissemination of information, news and educational resources and activities as well managing events, stocks and other relevant information for OSHubs. This web framework will be based on open-source software *Django*. These web frameworks have been co-developed by the P1-IAU and P2-ULEI. These frameworks have been used for some of the most visited educational and outreach websites in Europe, such as the IAU, ESA/NASA Hubble Space Telescope¹⁵, ESO¹⁶, Universe Awareness¹⁷, EU Space Awareness¹⁸. The web framework will allow the project to develop a cohesive web presence and prepare websites in (at least) 9 OpenAstroSchools languages, to support local dissemination initiatives. The format of the existing web frameworks makes expansion to other languages simple, with fast and low-cost development. Specific modules to produce, manage, translate and distribute educational materials have already been developed for the web framework. The framework allows the author of the resource to update the content of the resource and automatically produce the necessary output files in the necessary formats (example: html, print ready PDFs, ePUBs (for eReaders like iPads, Kindles or iPhones) and also source files and .doc files for translations). This will also allow a direct update of the activities through an API (application programming interface) to the generic resources databases (such as OERCommons, Scientix, TES, ISSU, Slideshare). The OpenAstroSchools digital platform will be kept at least 3 years after the duration of the project and can be used to future projects by the European Union around challenges. Publications using persistent existing media, notably journals in the astronomy and wider educational communities, will preserve the OpenAstroSchools legacy over a considerably longer period of time.

The sections below describe all OpenAstroSchools target audiences, dissemination channels and the measures that will be applied to reach them and maximise the impact. The sections also describe a set of communication products that will be created to achieve the expected impact for each specific target group.

Target audiences and dissemination channels

Students: OpenAstroSchools will distribute posters and brochures, develop an active presence on social media, and disseminate specifically to parents, teachers and schools (see sections below on formal educators and school governance), as well as explore possibilities for guerilla marketing to reach youth.

Formal educators: To effectively reach formal educators throughout Europe, OpenAstroSchools will apply a local, national, European and international approach. Locally, OpenAstroSchools partners will use the local partnerships and leverage their existing communication channels (e.g.: teachers-centred websites and publications, textbook publishers) and teacher networks (e.g. national teachers associations). Local partners will also disseminate OpenAstroSchools activities, products and resources at regional and national levels, through networks and at relevant events (e.g.: teachers congresses or meetings). OpenAstroSchools partners will also approach local vocational school and provide information and teacher training at national teacher events. Relevant information and resources will also be disseminated through existing teacher networks and existing repositories on European and international level. Each OpenAstroSchools partner will also exploit their existing teacher networks to expand OpenAstroSchools reach of formal educators (see Table 2.2). Finally, OpenAstroSchools will leverage its membership on relevant formal education social media groups (e.g.: Science teachers in Europe and Galileo Teachers Facebook groups) to share OpenAstroSchools resources. Specific resources targeted at formal educators will be developed, from basic information packages outlining the Open Schools methodology and the OpenAstroSchools specifics to more detailed treatments based on lessons learned and evaluation results. OpenAstroSchools will disseminate newsletters, short articles, posters and leaflets, and develop an active social media presence to reach formal educators (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and explore new media if relevant at that time). All OpenAstroSchools products and resources will be freely available on the Digital OpenAstroSchools platform to download, adapt and share.

STEAM informal and non-formal education communities (national, European and global): The Digital OpenAstroSchools platform will serve as a common repository for all OpenAstroSchools products and resources. To maximise reach, OpenAstroSchools will also publish all open access resources, as well as the auxiliary materials with additional information about the context and concepts of the project, on existing national, European and

15 <http://www.spacetelescope.org>

16 <http://www.eso.org>

17 www.eu-unawe.org

18 www.space-awareness.org

international Open Educational Resources repositories, namely Scientix, OERCommons, Open Education Europa, Schoolbordportaal¹⁹, and TES Education²⁰. These resources will be promoted in national and European informal and non-formal education networks and initiated by other European projects, like Scientix, Ecsite, TEMI, EU Space Awareness²¹, etc. The STEAM education communities will also be reached at international conferences such as Ecsite Annual Conference (museums and science centres), PCST – Public Communication of Science and Technologies 2018 conference (scholars and practitioners in the science communication), Eucu.net conferences (the network of children universities), Fab Learn and participation in Scientix Networking events. OpenAstroSchools partners (P2-UL, P4-TCD) run training courses for science communicators, museums staff, scientists and other people involved in science communication activities (for example JCOM Masterclasses²² and masters programmes in Science Communication²³), and will disseminate project results through these programmes in the years to come. OpenAstroSchools will also use existing mailing lists for this target audience (such as PSCI-COM²⁴ and International Network on Public Communication of Science and Technology²⁵).

University educators and researchers: OpenAstroSchools partners are part of 4 university and research networks (see Table 2.2) and in addition, all local OpenAstroSchools have established partnerships with research institutes. Through these partnerships, OpenAstroSchools will involve university educators and researchers in the co-development and implementation of OpenAstroSchools activities. Specifically, OpenAstroSchools will exploit existing mailing lists (e.g.: P1-IAU and P2-ULEI internal mailing list and alumni mailing list, P1-IAU OAE National Astronomy Education Coordinators, P1-IAU OAO National Outreach Coordinators), websites of partner research networks research unions (e.g.: European Physical Society, International Astronomical Union), and academies of science and humanities (e.g.: ALLEA²⁶) and leverage participation at relevant conferences, to reach this target audience. OpenAstroSchools will send newsletters, publish updates on existing websites and disseminate posters and leaflets at relevant events. In-depth descriptions aimed at this target group will point out ways that OpenAstroSchools lessons-learned as well as the Open School methodology in general can be used by target group members in their own subject areas and their own communities.

Industry: 30 space related enterprises will be directly engaged with OpenAstroSchools.. Whenever possible, OpenAstroSchools will work closely with other Maker professionals (e.g.: carpenters, electricians, farmers, engineers, and artists).

Local and/or regional government and other policy makers: Reaching policy makers, local and national advocacy lobbying. OpenAstroSchools academic research and evaluation results to inform policy.

Media: OpenAstroSchools will connect with media networks on an international, European, national/regional and local level. Through press releases for relevant events and invitations to local OpenAstroSchools events. In addition, consortium partners will leverage their media networks to disseminate OpenAstroSchools press releases.

Vehicles for creating OpenAstroSchools impact

The activities will be rolled out through the key channels of consortium partners and dissemination nodes shown in Table 2.5. The estimated reach is based on the relevant figures provided by the consortium partners and on previous projects. Special emphasis will be put on social media, which has demonstrated substantial influence in changing in educational and pedagogical thinking in the last decade. The current value of information shared promptly when it is first available and accessible at one's fingertip demonstrates the value of open education. To enhance engagement with students, teachers and beyond, the project will implement a social learning experience through key social media networks to disseminate content and network. To grow this network, OpenAstroSchools will use the existing social media networks of the project partners which consist of 18 active Facebook pages in total with a fanbase of about 180 000 and 18 active Twitter accounts with more than 150 000 followers, this will provide a > 400 000 estimated reach through social media. The social network will not only focus on disseminating content, but also on listening to the audience (children and youth) and engaging accordingly. In all these cases, OpenAstroSchools has a hierarchical strategies: on a social media level, we will get out the message about the excitement and community engagement created by the project. For those who want to dig deeper, we have in-depth descriptions of the methodologies, lessons-learned and (eventual) evaluation results for the OpenAstroSchools, in a suitably general Open Schools context that would allow interested parties to adapt the concept for their own fields on the one hand and for their own communities on the other.

19 National repository in the Netherlands: <http://www.schoolbordportaal.nl/index.html?>

20 www.scientix.eu, www.oercommons.org, <http://openeducationeuropa.eu/>, www.tes.com

21 <http://www.ecsite.eu/>, <http://www.teachingmysteries.eu/>, <http://www.space-awareness.org/en/>

22 <http://jcom.sissa.it/masterclasses/>

23 mcs.sissa.it and <https://www.universiteitiden.nl/en/science/science-communication-and-society> and <https://www.tcd.ie/Education/courses/masters/science/>

24 PSCI-COM@JISCMAIL.AC.UK

25 <http://www.pcast.co/discussion>

26 <http://www.allea.org/Pages/ALL/4/775.bGFuZz1FTkc.html>

Table 2.1. Vehicles for creating impact

Channel	Description	Estimated reach
OpenAstroSchools and Partner websites	OpenAstroSchools website content will be available in (at least) 6 languages (English, French, German, Greek, Dutch and Portuguese). Relevant updates and announcements will be posted weekly. The announcements will be written by OpenAstroSchools managers and other activity leaders and participants. All the relevant announcements will also be posted on partners websites. Estimated reach is based on website analytics from previous projects and partners websites.	750 000
Social media	OpenAstroSchools will use different social media channels to engage with the respective target audiences. These channels will include Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and YouTube (especially with simple videos of activities) and explore the possibility to use TikTok. If necessary OpenAstroSchools will use other social media channels that will be relevant at the time of the implementation.	400 000
Newsletters	OpenAstroSchools will distribute 5 newsletters between M4-M26, when appropriated local versions will be distributed as well. Some of the updates and relevant information will be included in the relevant partners newsletters.	30 000
Events	OpenAstroSchools will organise direct activities for school groups. 100 activities for the communities, including community participatory workshops and hackathons with schools, local stakeholders and experts, participation in relevant national and European conferences, workshops and other community events.	10 000
Media (including TV, Press, and social media influencers e.g.: bloggers or YouTubers)	At least 4 press releases during the project, namely M3: OpenAstroSchools project announced, M6: European-wide mission-oriented challenges announced M12: Results from the hackathon, M26: Final projects outcomes. Press releases will be distributed online and using the Press Information channels from partner organisations. Relevant media will be invited to all the OpenAstroSchools activities.	10 000 (Media reach) around 1 000 000 media engagements.
Key Opinion (Digital) Leaders	OpenAstroSchools will engage with relevant opinion leaders and influencers, such as local and global social media influencers ²⁷ (Young people with thousands of views of their videos on YouTube channel). These will maximise the reach of the project.	5000 (Key Opinion Leaders) around 250 000 engagements.

In summary, based on the data from our consortium's previous projects the expected number of teachers, young people and members of the wider society to be reached by OpenAstroSchools communication initiatives over 2 years is about 1 million.

²⁷ [http://www.fastcompany.com/3028278/the-fast-growing-profitable-market-for-teenage-influencer-endorsements-on-twitter-instagram-](http://www.fastcompany.com/3028278/the-fast-growing-profitable-market-for-teenage-influencer-endorsements-on-twitter-instagram)

3. Implementation

3.1. Work plan – Work packages and deliverables

3.1.1. Overall work Plan

The OpenAstroSchools implementation plan combines a set of specific tasks and components necessary for achieving the strategic objectives set in Section 1 with the skills, competencies and networks provided by the consortium partners. Open-AstroSchools is envisioned as a 26-month project and is divided into 7 work packages (WP). All the work packages support a high quality implementation through a credible approach and efficient coordination and support measures (Figure 3.1).

Fig. 3.1. Pert chart of OpenAstroSchool work packages, their main concepts and components. All the OpenAstroSchool work packages will feed into the “on the ground” impacts, namely students, educators and schools.

WP1 (Manage) will set-up and implement the management infrastructure and develop the appropriate organizational structures that will allow the consortium to achieve the objectives and the requirements of the call; WP2 (Mission-Oriented Open Schooling) will develop and coordinate the implementation of innovative European-wide mission-oriented challenges on Open Schooling; WP3 (Direct Impact Through Open Schoolings) will be the interface to reach directly to the education stakeholders (schools, students and educators) and their local community; WP4 (Disseminate & Broadening Impacts) will broaden the impact of the project worldwide and will promote the OpenAstroSchools activities, resources, research results, field and assessment to the different stakeholder groups; WP5 (Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation) will assess the impact and learning processes of OpenAstroSchools activities and interventions in all the identified target audiences; and WP6 (Legacy, Sustainability & Advocacy) will advocate for a bigger role for research and innovation in schools through open schooling and develop and implement a sustainability plan for the project. WP7 (Ethics) will develop and monitor the ethics dimension of the project. P1-IAU²⁸ will coordinate the OpenAstroSchools consortium (Detailed role of partners in section 3.3. Consortium as a whole).

The detailed work package content is detailed in the WP description tables and Gantt chart can be found in Tables 3.1a and Figure 3.2.

²⁸ At the time of stage-1, P2-ULEI was the coordinator, but the consortium has decided that P1-IAU is better placed to coordinate a transnational project due to its international offices and global network of professionals.

Activities	Phase I: Open school Challenges Development					Phase II: Challenges Journey						Phase III: Local Implementation								Phase IV: Closure								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26		
Project Month																												
Milestones	M7.1	M1.1	M4.1			M3.1 M5.1	M2.1				M3.2	M2.2											M3.3	M		M5.2		
WP1 – Management												D1.1															D1.2	
T1.1 Set up and run the management infrastructure																												
T1.2 Set up and run the project monitoring system																												
T1.3 Consortium Meetings																											D2.2	D2.3
WP2 – Mission-Oriented Open Schooling								D2.1																				
T2.1. Develop European-wide mission-oriented challenges with an Open Schooling approach and respective on-line platform																												
T2.2. Engage students, educators and relevant stakeholders in the challenges																												
T2.3. Organise and implement the selection process for the selected teams and organise the final Hackathon																												
WP3 – Direct Implementation Through Open Schooling				D3.1								D3.2 D3.3					D3.4							D3.5 D3.6		D3.7		
T3.1 Implementation Plan																												
T3.2 OpenAstroSchools Communities of Practice																												
T3.3 Workshops and Training Activities																												
T3.4 OpenAstroSchools Tool-kit																												
T3.5 Pilot Open Schooling																												
WP4 – Disseminate & Broadening Impacts						D4.1							D4.2												D4.3		D4.4	
T4.1. Identifying target groups for dissemination of project innovations and results																												
T4.2. Develop materials and communication products for external communication																												
T4.3. Disseminate the information material to members of the target group																												
T4.4 Coordinate Special Issue of Open Schools Journal for Open Science (OSJ)																												
WP5 – Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation						D5.1				D5.2						D5.3											D5.4	
T5.1 Review the current state of the field																												
T5.2 Develop tailored research instruments																												
T5.3 Facilitate ongoing project feedback																												
T5.4 Create an open-access Impact Evaluation Toolkit																												
WP6 – Legacy, Sustainability & Advocacy						D6.1																				D6.2	D6.3	
T6.1 Preparing the ground for the sustainability of OpenAstroSchools																												
T6.2 Produce and distribute Policy Briefings on the highlight the important role of open schooling for research and innovation education																												
T6.3 Advocacy actions with textbook publishers and advocate for the use of open schooling resources in formal textbooks																												
T6.4 Advocacy initiatives at National and EU Levels for sustainability of open schooling actions in the long-term																												
WP7 – Ethics	D7.1																											
T7.1 Obtain ethical approval																												

Table 3.1a: List of work packages

Work package No	Work Package Title	Lead Participant No	Lead Participant Short Name	Person-Months	Start Month	End month
1	Manage	1	IAU	21	1	26
2	Mission-Oriented Open Schooling	2	ULEI	34	1	26
3	Direct Impact Through Open Schooling	3	EA	43	1	26
4	Disseminate & Broadening Impacts	1	IAU	20	1	26
5	Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation	4	TCD	29.5	1	26
6	Legacy, Sustainability & Advocacy	2	ULEI	13	1	26
7	Ethics	4	TCD	0.5	1	26

Table 3.1b: Work packages descriptions

Work package number	1	Lead beneficiary	IAU							
Work package title	Management									
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name of participant	IAU	ULEI	EA	TCD	CEspace	ULimburg	OEWf	Nuclio	NOA	UAntwerpen
Person months per participant:	8	4	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
Start month	1	End month	26							

Objectives

The WP main objective is to coordinate the OpenAstroSchool activities and to maintain an efficient relationship between the project partners, stakeholders and the European Commission. In particular, this Work Package (in collaboration with WP5) intends to achieve the highest standards of quality of deliverables, and to do so on time and within budget. The specific objectives are:

- Set up the management infrastructure of the project, including management tools (internal communication and innovation management);
- Manage the project overall to achieve the project objectives and the requirements of the Call;
- Ensure the implementation of project activities on time and as described in the proposal;
- Address potential issues and take corrective actions if necessary.

Description of work

The work package is led by P1-IAU. All partners are involved in the project management, internal communications activities, and the production of deliverables and reports.

Task 1.1. Set up and run the management infrastructure (M1-M26, Lead: P1-IAU with inputs from all other partners)

- Organise and set up internal communication tools and activities: regular consortium meetings, internal work package meetings, communications platforms (e.g.: Basecamp or Slack), document-sharing platform (e.g: G Suite), innovation management tools (e.g: Viima).

- Set-up an innovation management plan: OpenAstroSchool will produce expected and unexpected innovative products and approaches. These will be captured and disseminated through the network through a specific innovation management plan.
- Develop and implement Intellectual Property Rights Management Plan suitable for wide dissemination to internal and external stakeholders and conforming, wherever possible, with the principles of Open Science through an appropriate use of licenses.
- Constitute the project advisory board (AB) including youth, schools and space enterprise representatives.
- Monitor the gender dimension in all aspects of the OpenAstroSchool project (from management structures to activities)
- Monitor risk and quality of implementation.

Task 1.2. Set up and run the project monitoring system (M1-M26, Lead: P1-IAU with inputs and participation from all other partners)

- Monitor each work package progress.
- Identify and address potential issues, take or propose corrective actions when necessary.
- Ensure the submission of all deliverables of the project on time.
- Coordinate the implementation and submission of the project periodic reports.
- Make sure that the project objectives are achieved with sufficient attention on the requirements of the grant agreement.
- Liaise and coordinate with European Commission and other relevant European institutions.
- Work closely with WP5: Evaluation leader to ensure that the identified issues in the implementation of the project are tackled accordingly.

Task 1.3 Consortium Meetings (M1-M26, Lead: P1-IAU with input and participation from all other partners, in particular the WP leaders)

- Organisation of kick-off meeting in M1 for all partners to be organised/hosted by P1-IAU.
- Organisation of additional face-to-face meeting (M12) for all partners to be hosted in one the partners premises.
- Organisation of Advisory Board virtual meeting every 4 months.

Deliverables

- **D1.1 First periodic report (M12):** report on activity implementation after Year 1 of the project.
- **D1.2 Final Report (M26):** report on activity implementation of the project.

If necessary, these reports, after discussion with the EC, can be integrated in the regular reporting periods

Work package number	2	Lead beneficiary	ULEI							
Work package title	Mission-Oriented Open Schooling									
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name of participant	IAU	ULEI	EA	TCD	CEspace	ULimburg	OEWf	Nuclio	NOA	UAntwerpen
Person months per participant:	4	14	5	1	3	2	3	3	3	3
Start month	1	End month	26							

Objectives

The main objective is to develop and implement three large European-wide open schooling challenges: Climate Action, Expanding Horizon, Life in the Universe. In particular, this Work Package (in collaboration with WP3) intends to engage with the direct target audience – Youth – through a series of local relevant challenges. The specific objectives are:

- Develop three European-wide mission-oriented challenges with an Open Schooling approach and respective challenge journeys;
- Develop the Mission-Oriented Open Schooling on-line platform;
- Engage students and their educators in these challenges;
- Identify and engage different stakeholders (educators, researchers, policy-makers, industries and civic society) to closely collaborate (e.g.: as mentors) with different student groups;
- Organise and implement the selection process for the winning teams;
- Organise the final Mission-Oriented Open Schooling Hackathon for selected teams;

Description of work

The work package is led by P2-ULEI. All partners are involved in the development and implementation and the production of deliverables and reports.

Task 2.1. Develop European-wide mission-oriented challenges with an Open Schooling approach and respective on-line platform (M1-M6, Lead: P2-ULEI with inputs and participation from all other partners)

- Establish the Mission Boards with European (and whenever necessary international) experts from education, academia, industry (LE and SMEs), civil society, youth organisation and parents organisations.
- Develop specific Open Schooling missions based on European Commission's approach Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union, this will be done in close collaboration with all the partners and external experts (when necessary).
- Develop the specific challenge journeys: Mission ideas submission, Ideas peer-review, Iteration with mentor teams per mission, Final review (Task 2.3) by an expert panel, and final selection. The challenge journeys will follow a design thinking approach. Namely: the scope and context for the challenge and respective mission, potential examples and additional resources. Detailed information about participation and evaluation criteria will be available.
- Develop the on-line platform for Mission-Oriented Open Schooling based on best practices on mission and challenges based digital platforms, such as openIDEO (www.openideo.com), MIT Solve (<https://solve.mit.edu>) and NASA Asteroid Grand Challenge (<https://www.nasa.gov/content/asteroid-grand-challenge>)

Task 2.2. Engage students, educators and relevant stakeholders in the challenges (M1-M24), Lead: P2-ULEI with inputs and participation from all other partners)

- Promote challenges and provide onboarding of students (with a focus on Europe)
- Identify and engage different stakeholders (educators, researchers, policy-makers, industries and civic society) to closely collaborate (e.g.: as mentors) with different student groups;
- Develop an online and face-to-face mentorship programme for mission teams.

Task 2.3. Organise and implement the selection process for the selected teams and organise the final Hackathon (M6-M12), Lead: P2-ULEI, co-lead: P3-EA with inputs and participation from all other partners)

- Setup a review panel for Mission projects (including consortium members, Advisory board members and selected experts).
- Define a rubric to the assessment of mission projects.
- Evaluate and select mission projects based on the rubric.
- Organise the OpenAstroSchools Hackathon: define programme, facilitators and methodology
- Develop and implement a strategy to disseminate the results of the Hackathon to the other projects and future initiatives, namely by the inclusion of findings, recommendation and best practices in the toolkit (task 3.5), organisation of a specific webinar, workshop in the Summer Schools (task 3.3) and a session in the MOOC (task 3.4).

Deliverables

- **D2.1 WP2 Progress Report (M8):** Report on platform and the 3 European-wide mission-oriented challenges.
- **D2.2 Stakeholders Engagement Report (M25):** Report on impact numbers and engagement level of relevant stakeholders.
- **D2.3 WP2 Final Report (M26):** Report on Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach and guidelines for future implementation.

Work package number	3	Lead beneficiary	EA							
Work package title	Direct Implementation Through Open Schooling									
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name of participant	IAU	ULEI	EA	TCD	CEspace	ULimburg	OEWF	Nuclio	NOA	UAntwerpen
Person months per participant:	2	2	12	1	5	4	5	5	5	2
Start month	1	End month	26							

Objectives

The main objectives of this work package are:

- Create and progressively build the community of schools that will open to industry, research, informal education settings, parents, policy makers and the general public
- Offer training to teachers/educators in the form of workshops, summer schools, online webinars and a MOOC specially designed around the OpenAstroSchool challenges.
- Create guidelines and support materials, namely the OpenAstroSchools Tool-kit, for schools in order to embrace the OpenAstroSchool approach
- Implement the OpenAstroSchool selected and proposed activities at a large scale in Europe and beyond.

Description of work

The work package is led by P3-EA . This work package will be in charge of the scaling up and uptake of Projects from Phase II and to be implemented by 500 schools within and outside Europe.

Task 3.1 Implementation Plan (M1-M3 Lead: EA with inputs and participation from all other partners)

- Development of a concrete and detailed implementation plan that will present the methodology adopted in the design of the planned activities and will serve as a practical guide of action for the whole period of large scale pilot implementation.
- Define all types of project activities along with the mechanisms that will be applied to monitor, guide and support the participants, mainly teachers and students.
- Develop a mechanism for monitoring implementation. Each implementation activity will be performed centrally but during implementation, the activity will also be managed locally by a partner in each of the pilot countries who will act as the National Coordinator, responsible for the local organization and localization of the project resources and activities.

Task 3.2 OpenAstroSchools Communities of Practice (M1-M26 Lead: EA with inputs and participation from all other partners)

- Identify and establish at least 7 Communities of Practice [Austria, Belgium, France, Greece, Ireland, the Netherlands and Portugal) in 7 EU countries. These communities are based in schools, science centres and institutions with several years of experience and expertise in reaching children, teenagers and their families. The OpenAstroSchool engagement nodes have been involved in several STEAM (STEM + Arts) and space educational activities
- Start from this core of 10 Communities of Practice along with some pre-selected schools around Europe (10 schools from the OSOS school-network have already identified), to increasingly build the community of stakeholders (teachers, students, parents, science educators, researchers, industry actors and policy makers) who will accompany the development of the OpenAstroSchools from the early phases till the full deployment of the project results into long term sustainability planning.
- Pilot schools clustering and networking. The participating school communities will be facilitated throughout the project to form an international network of schools, with exchanges and collaborations within communities of practice emerging in homogeneous clusters (e.g. those who take up the same OpenAstroSchool challenge) as well as across the whole network.
- Development of flexible structures and initiatives in the course of the project (e.g. mission-based framework approach) which schools and educational systems will be able to adopt and maintain afterwards sustaining the OpenAstroSchools network of communities of practice.

Task 3.3 Organization of OpenAstroSchool Summer Schools (M11, M23) Lead: EA with inputs from all other partners)

- Organization of in-service training seminars for teachers and teachers' trainers involved in the project in the form of two OpenAstroSchool Summer Schools, one on each summer within the lifetime of the project
- Selection of participating teachers by the OpenAstroSchool engagement nodes.
- Disseminate and open to other teachers that can participate under the framework of the ERASMUS+ Action. The expenses of the realization of these activities for this extended group of teachers will be covered from the grants that they could receive from their National Agencies.

Task 3.4 Development of MOOC on Mission-based Open Schooling (M6, M12 Lead: EA with inputs from all other partners)

- Development of the OpenAstroSchools MOOC (around M4-M6) that will introduce to all involved stakeholders (main target remains teachers/educators) the Mission-based Open Schooling approach and guide them step-by-step through the OpenAstroSchools platform that will be used for all Mission-projects. The MOOC will empower teachers from all levels of education as well as leaders of extracurricular activities and parents to follow this new Open schooling by creating ambitious missions that have the potential to have wide societal impact. This will need a combination of using existing technologies and new ideas that can drive a systemic change e.g. in the way science is taught in schools (mission-based projects vs. stand-alone projects) or the way schools are connected to the local community (open schools vs. isolated schools). The resources from the EU SPACE AWARENESS, Space Scoops, and ESERO will be used to enrich the available challenge-resources area of the MOOC and provide up-to-date practices of teaching topics related to our Grand Challenges in science classrooms and in informal settings.
- Updated version of the MOOC (offered in M12) focusing in the last phase of the three Grand Challenges selected mission-projects, as well as in the Hackathon (process and requirements).
- Organisation of at least 2 online events (webinars) in the framework of the MOOC in order to show the variety of free resources that educators can easily adapt to their classrooms' needs. During the online events, participants will become familiar with practical tips on the use of the resources highlighted in the MOOC. The advantage of these online events is that teachers from all over Europe will be able to connect from their locations and exchange best practices and ideas for the upcoming challenges with their colleagues.

Task 3.5 OpenAstroSchools Toolkit (M1-M24 Lead: EA with inputs and participation from all other partners)

- Develop a series of guidelines and support materials for the teachers and the students that will be involved in the implementation process. The materials will be available in conventional and electronic format (through the project's website).
- As the creation of the tool-kit will be based on the OpenAstroSchool challenges three different OpenAstroSchool Challenge Guides are expected to be provided during the lifetime of the project. The guides will be available in 6 languages (English, French, German, Greek, Dutch and Portuguese). Further translations into other languages will be explored via the IAU Translation Network. The first guide will be designed in M3 and delivered before the launch of the Grand Challenge while the second guide (full school version) will be delivered in M11.

Deliverables

- **D3.1 Implementation Plan (M4)** : This deliverable will be the main outcome of the work that will be performed in the framework of task T3.1. It will include a concrete and detailed plan of the preparation of the selected OAS activities on the field, and the corresponding mechanisms for monitoring the implementation.
- **D3.2 Interim Report on Implementation Activities (M12)**: This report will document the Implementation Activities at local, national and International level during the first year.
- **D3.3 Guidelines and Supporting Materials for Teachers and Students (M12)**: Guidelines and support materials for the students of the pilot schools as well as for the teachers that will be involved in the implementation process.
- **D3.4 OpenAstroSchool MOOC on Mission-based Open Schooling (M18)**: Report on the development and uptake of the OpenAstroSchool MOOC
- **D3.5 OpenAstroSchool Communities of Practice (M24)**: Report on the establishment of nodes and the development of development of communities or practice (open school networks)
- **D3.6 OpenAstroSchool Summer Schools report (M24)**: Report on the organisation, aims and impact of the OAS summer schools
- **D3.7 Final Report on Implementation Activities (M26)**: This report will document the Implementation Activities at local, national, European and international level

Work package number	4	Lead beneficiary	IAU							
Work package title	Disseminate & Broadening Impacts									
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name of participant	IAU	ULEI	EA	TCD	CEspace	ULimburg	OEFWF	Nuclio	NOA	UAntwerpen
Person months per participant:	8	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Start month	1	End month	26							

Objectives

The main objective is to disseminate insights and experiences from the project to a wider community, ensuring that innovations from the project will have the broadest possible impact beyond the scope of project partners and participants. This involves broker and communicator roles in putting the information available within the consortium into a format suitable for communicating them to external institutions and stakeholders. The specific objectives are:

- Identify stakeholders in and beyond Europe that are likely to benefit from the insights and innovations of the project, with a special emphasis on the astronomy education and space education community
- Create supporting material needed for external stakeholders to learn about the OpenAstroSchools project in general, as well as in preparation for understanding the specific results and innovations to be shared – including resources based on the material (MOOC, toolkit, How-To) created for internal training for the participating schools and institutions.
- Create suitable information products for dissemination for insights, experiences and innovations derived from the mission phases and competition.
- Use the previously identified channels to disseminate the aforementioned insights to suitable specific stakeholders and the education community in general.

Description of work

The work package is led by P1-IAU. All partners are involved in supporting the dissemination effort and providing input for the deliverables.

Task 4.1. Identifying target groups for dissemination of project innovations and results (M1-M10, lead P1-IAU with contributions from all the partners)

- Via the IAU Office of Astronomy for Education (OAE) and making use of the OAE's network of National Astronomy Education Coordinators (NAECS), identify stakeholders in the astronomy education community that could benefit from such dissemination
- Using the networks of our partners and actors like ESA, identify stakeholders in the space education community that could benefit from such dissemination
- Within the wider European education community, identify institutions and projects where actors could benefit from such dissemination
- Within the wider European education community, identify communication channels (such as specific journals or newsletters) that could be used for wider dissemination
- Pull the information obtained together into an external communication plan, to be updated as the project evolves

Task 4.2. Develop materials and communication products for external communication (M1-M26, lead P1-IAU with contributions from all the partners)

- Transform the OpenAstroSchools Toolkit into a resource that can be used by interested parties outside the consortium and partner schools, by adding context and documentation.
- Supplement the non-interactive parts of the OpenAstroSchools method MOOC for better usability by external viewers
- Create general supporting material for communicating the basic concepts of OpenAstroSchools and the underlying methodology to stakeholders who are not participants
- Based on the experiences from WP2 and WP3 activities, and incorporating results from WP5 as they become available, prepare information in a format suitable for dissemination to the target group

Task 4.3. Disseminate the information material to members of the target group (M7-M26, lead P1-IAU with contributions from all partners)

- Make the information products available on the project website
- Disseminate information products using the specific communication channels identified in Task 4.1.

Task 4.4 Coordinate Special Issue of Open Schools Journal for Open Science (OSJ) (M13-M26, lead P3-EA with contributions from all the partners)

- The Open Schools Journal for Open Science²⁹ is the first European peer reviewed scientific journal, which accepts original papers written by school age students on all aspects of STEM. Publication is free of charge and the Journal carries articles in various languages.
- Open a call for papers related to the OpenAstroSchools Challenges
- Collect, peer review (OSJ committee), edit and publish the articles in a Special Issue of OSJ

Deliverables

- **D4.1 Communication plan:** Overview of target group definition, including lists specifying the members of the target group at whom dissemination efforts will be aimed, will also include a Basic information package: Introduction to the concepts and methodology of OpenAstroSchools (M6)
- **D4.2 OpenAstroSchools information package:** Information material based on the guidelines and support materials for the students of the pilot schools (M13)
- **D4.3 Interim external communications report** – report on the actions implemented as part of the external communication strategy (M24)
- **D4.4 Special Issue of OSJ** Publication of a Special Issue of OSJ with articles reflecting upon the work performed by students during the OpenAstroSchools Challenges (M26)

Work package number	5	Lead beneficiary	TCD							
Work package title	Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation									
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name of participant	IAU	ULEI	EA	TCD	CEspace	ULimburg	OEWf	Nuclio	NOA	UAntwerpen
Person months per participant:	2	2	2	17.5	1	1	1	1	1	1
Start month	1	End month	26							

Objectives

The overall aim of this work package is to assess the impact of the project on all participants — schools, local communities, Civil Society Organisations, universities, and industry partners — as well as determining the effectiveness of the project in order to provide guidance and support to other organisations and projects working in the field of open schooling. The Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation Work Package has 5 key objectives:

- To review the current state of the field of open schooling and ascertain the best way to measure the impact of OpenAstroSchools on scientific interest, scientific literacy, and awareness of scientific careers.
- To develop, pilot, and validate research instruments to enable a high-quality evaluation of the impact.
- To analyse the findings of the evaluation and produce an open-access Impact Evaluation Toolkit to aid knowledge-sharing and future work in this field.
- To share a set of tailored indicators to help determine the effectiveness of community building, managing, and nurturing open schooling approaches.
- To publish the findings of the impact assessment in open access peer-reviewed journals in the field of education and engagement.

Description of work

This work package will assess the impact of OpenAstroSchools in local communities to foster improved science education for all citizens. It will evaluate the development of partnerships between schools, local communities, and local industry as well as a contribution to a more scientifically interested and literate society and awareness of (and interest in) scientific careers. The work package will provide on-going assessment of OpenAstroSchools which will be made publicly available to help provide citizens and future researchers with the tools and skills to make informed decisions and choices in this area. By evaluating the impact of OpenAstroSchools and producing an open-access Impact Evaluation Toolkit — the project will contribute towards the ERA objectives of increasing the numbers of scientists and researchers in Europe.

Task 5.1 Review the current state of the field (M1-M6, Lead: P4-TCD)

- Assess the field of open schooling evaluation and learn from all existing baseline datasets and open-access tools from other European open schooling projects.
- Build on the current state of the art to design an evaluation strategy that does not duplicate the work of existing projects but instead can address the more complex challenges of effectively evaluating the impact of open schooling.

Task 5.2 Develop tailored research instruments (M4-M10, Lead: P4-TCD, with all partners participating)

- Create a set of quantitative and qualitative evaluation tools building on the review work carried out in Task 5.1.
- Pilot and validate research instruments with all project partners participating and providing feedback.

Task 5.3 Facilitate ongoing project feedback (M1-M26, Lead: P4-TCD, with all partners participating)

- Facilitate dialogue and feedback mechanisms for all project partners to share their experience of the effectiveness of the project.
- Share learnings across all partners and build a suite of best practices for the Impact Evaluation Toolkit (D5.4).

Task 5.4 Create an open-access Impact Evaluation Toolkit (M20-M26, Lead: P4-TCD)

- Analyse the project findings and target appropriate open-access journals for the publication of results and learnings.
- Develop, share, and promote an open-access toolkit that equips future researchers and practitioners in the field with the tools and skills to have a meaningful impact in the area of open schooling.

Deliverables

- **D5.1 Report on Current State of the Field (M6):** A report on open schooling evaluation that considers existing datasets and tools from other open schooling projects and builds on those learnings to create a more effective evaluation strategy for OpenAstroSchools.
- **D5.2 Research Instruments (M10):** Bespoke evaluation tools based on the learnings from the review (D5.1) and the piloting and validating process carried out with all project partners.
- **D5.3 Interim Report on Evaluation (M15):** An assessment of learnings at the project midpoint taking into account the review of the field, tools developed, and ongoing feedback from all partners on the effectiveness of the project.
- **D5.4 Impact Evaluation Toolkit (M26):** An open-access toolkit that will help other individuals and organisations working in the area of open schooling to learn from the OpenAstroSchools experience and to utilise shared tools, resources, and best practices.

The overall final report on project effectiveness will be included in the project’s final report.

Work package number	6	Lead beneficiary	ULEI							
Work package title	Legacy, Sustainability & Advocacy									
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name of participant	IAU	ULEI	EA	TCD	CEspace	ULimburg	OEWf	Nuclio	NOA	UAntwerpen
Person months per participant:	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Start month	1	End month	26							

Objectives

This WP will study the sustainability and legacy of OpenAstroSchools. WP6 will also advocate for a wider use of open schooling approaches resources in school textbooks in some European countries. OpenAstroSchools will engage with national and European policymakers to highlight the important role of open schooling for research and innovation education. Specific objectives:

- To develop and implement a legacy and sustainability strategy for the OpenAstroSchools.
- To develop and implement an advocacy strategy for OpenAstroSchools, namely towards textbook publishers, and policy-makers at the National and European levels.

Description of work

The work package is led by P2-ULEI. All partners are involved in the project management, internal communications activities, and the production of deliverables and reports.

Task 6.1 – Preparing the ground for the sustainability of OpenAstroSchools beyond Horizon 2020 funding (M10-M26, Lead: PI-IAU)

- Study the feasibility to include Open Schooling in the curriculum at the national level (inputs)
- Develop a strategy to disseminate educational resources beyond the lifetime of the project.
- Develop a strategy to disseminate knowledge outcomes within established networks.
- Develop a strategy to integrate knowledge outcomes in relevant programmes run by the partners on a permanent basis.

Task 6.2 Produce and distribute Policy Briefings on the highlight the important role of open schooling for research and innovation education (M1-M26, Leader: P2-ULEI)

- Identify key topics for the policy makers
- Plan and understand the needs from the policy-maker
- Produce the briefings based on inputs from consortium, advisory board and external experts
- Present the briefing to national and european policy-makers
- Distribute the briefing widely through OpenAstroSchools channels (in collaboration with WP4)

Task 6.3 Advocacy actions with textbook publishers and advocate for the use of open schooling resources in formal textbooks (M1-M26, Leader: P2-ULEI)

- Identify key national textbook publishers and understand their needs;
- Work closely with the European educational publishers (e.g: European Educational Publishers Group) to identify open schooling projects and resources for textbooks;

Task 6.4 Advocacy initiatives at National and EU Levels for sustainability of open schooling actions in the long-term (M10-M26, Leader: P1-ULEI)

- Identification of important stakeholders at EU level with interest in space sector, education and public outreach
- Explore the feasibility to use the
- Lobbying actions with Members of the European Parliament and other policy-makers at EU level
- Organisation of policy event (e.g.:Dinner Debate) about the importance of open schooling for research and innovation education.

Deliverables

- **D6.1 Sustainability plans for OpenAstroSchools (M6)**
- **D6.2 Policy briefing on the role of open schooling in research and innovation (M24)**
- **D6.3 Report on advocacy actions for use of open schooling approaches in formal textbooks (M26)**

The overall Final Report on WP6 will be included on the project's final report.

Work package number	7	Lead beneficiary	TCD							
Work package title	Ethics									
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name of participant	IAU	ULEI	EA	TCD	CEspace	ULimburg	OEWf	Nuclio	NOA	UAntwerpen
Person months per participant:	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0
Start month	1	End month	26							

Objectives

The aim of Work Package 7 is to ensure that OpenAstroSchools applies fundamental ethical principles and legislation to all of the work carried out. The objective is:

- To obtain ethical approval for all project activities and establish a data management plan in compliance with fundamental ethical principles and the European Commission’s guidelines on FAIR data management

Description of work

The work package is led by P4-TCD (in close collaboration with P1-IAU), since it will be responsible for Work Package 5 Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation, TCD will be responsible for obtaining ethical approval and for managing the research data. A Data Protection Officer at Trinity College Dublin will provide guidance on the data management plan. This will define the type of quantitative and qualitative data that the project will use, the collection/generation methods in accordance with the “data minimisation principle”, the encryption of digital devices, data verification, access, and preservation. An open access repository maintained at Trinity College Dublin (TARA: <http://www.tara.tcd.ie>) will be utilised for data curation and preservation.

Task 7.1 Obtain ethical approval (M1, Lead: P1-IAU and P4-TCD)

- An ethics application that adheres to the European Commission’s guidelines on FAIR data management and EU General Data Protection Regulation will be created and submitted to the Research Ethics Committee at Trinity College Dublin along with samples of informed consent/assent forms and information sheets.

Deliverables

- **D7.1 Data Management Plan (M1):** The data management plan will be finalised once ethical approval has been granted that describes the technical and organisational measures that will be implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the participants.

Table 3.1c: List of Deliverables³⁰

Deliverable (number)	Deliverable name	Work package number	Short name of lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery date (in months)
D1.1	First periodic report	1	IAU	R	PU	M12
D1.2	Final Report	1	IAU	R	PU	M26
D2.1	WP2 Progress Report	2	ULEI	R	PU	M8
D2.2	Stakeholders Engagement Report	2	ULEI	R	PU	M25
D2.3	WP2 Final Report	2	ULEI	R	PU	M26
D3.1	Implementation Plan	3	EA	R	PU	M4
D3.2	Interim Report on Implementation Activities	3	EA	R	PU	M12
D3.3	Guidelines and Supporting Materials for Teachers and Students	3	EA	R	PU	M12
D3.4	OpenAstroSchool MOOC on Mission-based Open Schooling	3	EA	R	PU	M18
D3.5	OpenAstroSchool Communities of Practice	3	EA	R	PU	M24
D3.6	OpenAstroSchool Summer Schools report	3	EA	R	PU	M24
D3.7	Final Report on Implementation Activities	3	EA	R	PU	M26
D4.1	Communication plan	4	IAU	R	PU	M6
D4.2	OpenAstroSchools information package	4	IAU	R	PU	M13
D4.3	Interim external communications report	4	IAU	R	PU	M24
D4.4	Special Issue of OSJ	4	EA	R	PU	M26
D5.1	Report on Current State of the Field	5	TCD	R	PU	M6
D5.2	Research Instruments	5	TCD	OTHER	PU	M10
D5.3	Interim Report on Evaluation	5	TCD	R	PU	M15

³⁰ If your action is taking part in the Pilot on Open Research Data, you must include a data management plan as a distinct deliverable within the first 6 months of the project. This deliverable will evolve during the lifetime of the project in order to present the status of the project's reflections on data management. A template for such a plan is available in the H2020 Online Manual on the Participant Portal.

D5.4	Impact Evaluation Toolkit	5	TCD	OTHER	PU	M26
D6.1	Sustainability plans for OpenAstroSchools	6	ULEI	R	PU	
D6.2	Policy briefing on the role of open schooling in research and innovation	6	ULEI	R	PU	M24
D6.3	Report on advocacy actions for use of open schooling approaches in formal textbooks	6	ULEI	R	PU	M26
D7.1	Data Management Plan	6	TCD	R	CI	M1

3.2. Management structure and procedures

3.2.1. Organisation structure and decision-making

The OpenAstroSchools project management structure is defined below including roles and responsibilities and interdependencies of the 10 partners involved in the project, as well as the operational project management and the management procedures.

The organisational structure of the consortium shall comprise the following bodies:

Project Board

Each partner organisation will appoint one representative for the Project Board (PB) that will control the good progress and implementation of the project. Chaired by the Project Coordinator (P1 – IAU) on its implementation. The PB will have overall responsibility for financial, administrative and exploitation aspects of the project. A consortium agreement will be written, that will specify contingency plans, such as the appointment of deputy project managers and budget reallocations. The PB guarantee the involvement of Project Managers to implement the activities for the ones they engaged at organisation level. The PB will have 2 face-to-face meetings during M1 (kick-off) and M12 (Start of implementation phase) and 8 video conference meetings once every three months (M3,M6,M9,M12,M15, M18, M21, M24).

Coordinator

P1-IAU as coordinator has the responsibility of making the consortium partners achieve the project objectives according to the timeline and requirements described in the grant agreement. P1-IAU will appoint a Project Manager (PM) to fulfil this role. The PM monitors the progress of each work package and makes sure that deadlines and objectives are met. The PM implements regular risk assessment, identifies potential issues, and proposes mitigations and solutions in relation with relevant partners. Other tasks involved keeping a database of members and other persons updated and available and collecting, reviewing to ensure quality and consistency and submit reports. The PM reports and discusses EU management aspects and potential serious issues with the European Commission. The PM will attend monthly WP meetings and organise WP leaders meetings every month. PM will be the leader of WP1.

Work Package Leaders

The day to day management of the project will be implemented by the work package leaders and managed by WP1 (PM), each responsible for the implementation of the activities described under their work packages (WP) and communication between the partners involved in the same WP. The WP leaders ensure the delivery of WP activities on time and according to the objectives described in the grant agreement. They provide guidance and consultancy to the Project Manager when necessary. They monitor the progress and quality of the work package activities, ensure the sub-

mission of related deliverables on time, and collect data for the assessment of the activities of the associated WP. WP leaders should raise any issue or failure to achieve objectives directly to the Project Coordinator. Work package leaders will meet once every two weeks under the initiative of the PM. Each WP leader will organise monthly WP meeting involving all partners involved in their respective activities.

Mission Board

The Mission challenges developed in the OpenAstroSchools project will be overseen by a Mission Board (MB). Three MBs (one per challenge) will be responsible for the mentorship of the mission projects. Each Mission Board will be composed of 5-7 people with a broad mix of experts from innovation, research, policy making, civil society and practitioner organisations. MBs will follow the implementation regularly and will review status reports from projects on the OpenAstroSchools digital platform as well as organising knowledge transfer sessions such as webinars with experts. MB Climate Change will be lead by P2-ULEI and will also include P3-EA and P6-UC LIMBURG; MB Expanding Horizon will be lead by P7-OEWF and will also include P5-CITE, P8-NUCLIO; and MB Life in the Universe will be lead by P9-NOA and will also include P1-IAU and P10-UANTWERPEN. Each MB leader will organise monthly MB meeting involving all partners involved in their respective activities.

Advisory Board

OpenAstroSchools will establish an Advisory Board (AB) that will meet virtually every 4 months. The task of the AB will be to both advise the PB on key aspects of the project and safeguard the project objectives. Each AB member will be selected for a special relevant expertise and will receive regular project reports from the coordinator. The appointment of members must be approved by the PB. Specific aspects of the project that will be safeguarded by the AB members include:

- relevance to young people (e.g.: a representative of Organising Bureau of European School Student Unions), Coordination with education system (e.g: policy-maker from an Education National Authority); gender & diversity balance, coordination with space industry (e.g.: European Association of Aeronautics, Space, Defence and Security Industries) and representative from ESA Education Office.

Internal Communication Channels

All participants in the project will share common communication and collaborative tools to ensure a good communication between partners.

- **Project Management Software:** A project management system will be setup to be used for the day-to-day project communications. Here partners can open a private and secure communication space. The platform allows to start discussions involving different partners, keep track of discussions, share a calendar, and important documents.
- **Project management approaches:** The project will implement different management approaches, depending on the activities that have been developed, e.g.: use Scrum for website development, Design Thinking for Challenges and missions.
- **Main communication tools:** Emails about specific issues and relevant for groups of partners will be the regular communications exchange tool. Project will also use daily communications tools like Slack and Basecamp.
- **PB meetings:** The Coordinator organises meetings with the PB every three months.
- **AB meetings:** The Coordinator organises an AB meeting every 4 months.
- **WP leaders meetings:** The Coordinator will organise WP leaders meetings every month.
- **MB Meetings:** The MB meetings will be organised by MB leaders and involve all partners involved in the activities of the related MB every month.
- **WP meetings:** The WP meetings will be organised by WP leaders and involve all partners involved in the activities of the related WP.
- **Other meetings:** Extra meetings will be organised as necessary with small groups of partners.

Decision Making Procedure

The day-to-day decision making will be made by the work packages leaders in coordination with the project coordinator. The PB will be informed of the day-to-day progress of the project and will make strategic decisions on topics relevant to the project as a whole. The AB will advise on those topics. Any serious issue or potential risk for the implementation of the project should be raised by Work Package leaders to the Coordinator. Any critical decision for the project will be discussed with the Project Board and raised to the EC Project Officer when necessary. Extraordinary consortium meetings can be organised in case of necessity or emergency.

Conflict Resolution

The Coordinator will endeavour to resolve any conflicts at the lowest possible level. Each WP Leader will be responsible to solve minor issues within a specific WP. In case of conflict between Partners, the respective Partner has to address the issue to the Coordinator first. The Coordinator shall first try to reconcile them and, if there is no resolution,

the Coordinator will call a meeting of the PB in order to find an acceptable solution to the problem. In terms of conflict resolution, active listening approaches will be used. If active listening fails to solve the conflict, a mediated arbitration will be pursued; in this case a member of the AB will be appointed as the chair of an arbitration panel (at least 3 parties non involved in the conflict).

3.2.2. Milestones

Table 3.2a: List of milestones

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related work packages	Due date (in month)	Means of verification
M1.1	Management Structures Established and Kick-Off meeting	1	M2	Report with specific names and roles in the different management structures and first kick-off meeting.
M2.1	European-wide Open Schooling Mission-oriented Challenges	1	M7	The first European-wide open schooling mission-oriented challenge is available online and digital platform is online.
M2.2	OpenAstroSchools Hackathon	2	M12	Report including the Hackathon programme and list of participants.
M3.1	OpenAstroSchools MOOC on Mission-based Open Schooling	2	M6	Launch of the MOOC with guidelines about the Mission-based Open Schooling approach and the participation in the OpenAstroSchools Challenges through the submission of Mission-projects
M3.2	1st OpenAstroSchools Summer School	2.4	M11	1st in-service training seminars for teachers / educators involved in the project
M3.3	Second consortium meeting at 2nd OpenAstroSchools Summer School	2.4	M23	Second consortium meeting at the time of the 2nd in-service training seminars for teachers and education stakeholders involved in the project
M4.1	Dissemination & Broadening Impacts Plan	2	M3	A comprehensive dissemination and communication plan, including strategies for broadening impacts of the project is available on-line for all the partners.
M5.1	Completion of open schooling evaluation review of the field	5	M6	A report on the state of the field that will guide the development of the evaluation tools.
M5.2	Sharing of Impact Evaluation Toolkit	5	M26	An open-access impact evaluation toolkit to help guide future work in the field.
M7.1	Ethical Approval	5	M1	A Data Management Plan.

3.2.3. Risk mitigation

In the following table (3.2b), the consortium estimates the potential risks that could become critical for implementation for the project and addresses them by proposing mitigation measures. This initial risk assessment will be used as a baseline for potential risks that could appear during the implementation of the project. Risk assessment will be performed at every step of the project and managed as to anticipate and minimise potential issues that may arise. Any identified issue that could become critical for the project achievement of its objectives will be raised and discussed with the EC Project Officer.

Table 3.2b: Critical risks for implementation

Description of risk (indicate level of likelihood: low/medium/high)	Work package(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Consortium partner withdraws. (Low)	WP1	If a partner withdraws, a suitable replacement will be found within the consortium and if necessary outside consortium.
A partner coordinator or manager withdraws or is incapacitated. (Medium)	All	Relevant partner needs to find a replacement within a month. If needed, relevant tasks will be transferred between partners. The Project Board involving representatives of each organisation are responsible for the good involvement of their organisation in the project.
The project failed to meet a milestone or deliverable. (Medium)	All	When the situation appears, the coordinator discusses the reasons for failure with the involved partners and reports to the EC Project Officer. When necessary, adapted corrective actions will be taken.
Insufficient reporting by partners on work/effort spent (Low)	WP1	All partners will assign experienced project managers and have a supporting administrating department or staff.
Deliverables not completed in full and on time (Low)	All	WP leaders monitor, alert, report problems to the Coordinator. WP leader and partners involved in the deliverable implement fall-back solution as per agreed plan. The Coordinator will contact the EC Project Officer if needed.
Ineffective internal communication tools (Low)	All	The Coordinator will establish internal communication tools applying the principles of good design, usability and interaction design, and will monitor their effectiveness. This will mitigate risks linked to bad users' and low level of usability.
A reduced interest of the target group (in particular schools) on participation in project activities (Medium/High)	WP2 and WP3	The main activities will start on M7, with the challenge announcement and there is chance of reduced interest from the targeted groups. However all partners have access to strong dissemination networks in their countries (and international) . All the partners have a track-record of organisation of large scale educational/public engagement activities.

Innovation Management

OpenAstroSchools will use an open innovation methodology to manage its innovation outputs. Open innovation is a systematic methodology to engage and steer resources to find solutions for specific opportunities and challenges with a project. For OpenAstroSchools this is especially important due to the diversity of expected submissions for missions. OpenAstroSchools innovation management will focus on cooperative and collaborative aspects of innovation management, namely: Connect to other projects, initiatives and stakeholders within and beyond OpenAstroSchools network; Screen landscape for stakeholders, identify and contact potential partners. Identify challenges and drivers for the collaboration. Align strategies and facilitate relations and translate potential synergies in a clear partnership; Determine what collaboration operating model will be and how partner can ensure objectives and cooperation are met. The open innovation methodology will be established by WP1 and will use specific software (e.g.: Viima) to follow the different steps for the innovation cycle. Whenever necessary this innovation management will be done in close collaboration with P2-ULEI: Centre for Innovation and Entrepreneurship.

3.3. Consortium as a whole

The OpenAstroSchools consortium is complementary in background skills, languages and experience. The range of expertise is multidisciplinary and multicultural. It includes astronomers with management experience, educators, experts in child development and outreach specialists. Each participant has several of the competencies required to carry out OpenAstroSchools, and additional expertise, which will greatly enhance the project as a whole. The participant organisations are working closely with national partners, such as the space and astronomical infrastructure organisations within their own countries and the national and local educational organisations. Pooling the resources and expertise across the 10 participating organisations will be cost effective and result in a project with added pan-European project value.

The OpenAstroSchools consortium brings to this proposal a unique combination of expertise:

- Expertise in leading Open Schooling: P3-EA is the coordinator of H2020 Open Schooling: Open Schools for Open Societies and P2-ULEI is the coordinator of H2020 Open Schooling: Open Science Hub Network
- Demonstrated ability and track record for carrying out the broad range of activities mandated in the Call with high impact,
- A link between the latest cutting edge exciting space science research and children and teenagers,
- A well-founded educational framework,
- An extremely broad dissemination network within Europe and globally with access to researchers, schools, teachers and national curricula – both bottom-up networks and top-down groupings,
- Cost-effectiveness, by exploiting and expanding the infrastructure and peer-review platform developed through the previous investment of FP7 and H2020,
- Connection with a university that is part of several large European space science research collaborations and access to some of the most creative European industrial entrepreneurs,
- Coordination between several diverse European space-oriented education and outreach activities to produce a “whole that is greater than the sum of the parts”.
- Extensive experience in creating and producing large scale awareness raising activities such as exhibitions.
- Experience gained in previous FP7 and H2020 projects and the global IAU Astronomy for Development network of reaching out to youth in underprivileged communities to help mobilise underexploited talent.
- Access to network of astronomy and physics education practitioners and scientists via P1-IAU and its Office of Astronomy for Education.

In particular, the different partners bring the following expertise to the consortium:

The **P1-IAU** comprises the largest organisations of professional astronomers with 13 679 members from over 100 nationalities. In addition to promote and safeguard the science of astronomy in all its aspects through international cooperation, the IAU also works to promote astronomical education, research and public outreach for the public. The organisation has great expertise on organising large-scale public engagement activities, including the UN/UNESCO International Year of Astronomy in 2009, which reached out to over 800 million people from 148 countries as well as the recent IAU 100th anniversary celebrations, which have reached millions of people worldwide with over 5000 activities in 134 countries. IAU also brings strong expertise on the establishment and coordination of hubs such as the Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD), a joint venture with the National Research Foundation (NRF) of South Africa as well as with the IAU Office for Astronomy Outreach (OAO) — a joint venture with the National Astronomical Observatory of Japan (NAOJ). The IAU Office of Young Astronomers, in close partnership with the Norwegian Academy organises an advanced training schools to future astronomers. Since 2018, the IAU is establishing an Office of Astronomy for Education (OAE), which will begin operations in late 2019/early 2020 focusing on formal pre-tertiary education. The role of the OAE is to support astronomers and astronomy educators in their astronomy education activities, This will involve infrastructure support and intensive networking among stakeholders.

P2-ULEI has an excellent track record of achieving high impact in implementing EC-funded educational projects in the astronomy/space field, such as the FP7 EU-UNAWA and the H2020 EU-SPACE AWARENESS. The organisation of educational and public engagement activities has established large networks in over 60 countries worldwide to reach out over 500 000 students and teachers since 2006. In addition, UL (i) coordinates the Citizen Science Lab, an incubator and central hub for citizen science efforts with a particular focus on astronomy, environmental science and Earth observations and (ii) hosts the International Astronomical Union European Regional Office of Astronomy for Development. UL has also a track record in communication, dissemination and advocacy.

P3-EA team has a systematic and exhaustive knowledge of the science curriculum in the Greek primary education, as it has been assigned to create the science text books for the last two grades of primary schools in Greece. Its work in EU projects over the last 15 years has established EA as a leading pioneer in innovative approaches to science education. Its R&D Department has coordinated and supported the participation of EA, either as coordinator or as partner, in more than 150 national and international collaborative research projects and networks (H2020, eContentPlus, ICT-PSP, SiS in FP7 and FP6, IST in FP5 and ICT in FP6, LLP-ICT, Socrates, Leonardo da Vinci, Erasmus+). EA team has implemented numerous projects and initiatives that combine ICT and STEM education, including as International Coordinator of the successful 335 000 Euro Odysseus FP7 DG E&I Space educational project to implement a pan-European Scientific Contest for teenagers aged 14 to 18 on Space exploration themes. Overall, EA has a very strong and proven experience in actively extending the dialogue between the scientific and the educational community.

As one of Ireland’s leading Universities, **P4-TCD** has world-class lab and classroom space, while Science Gallery Dublin has exhibition and gallery spaces, as well as public workshop and event space. TDC draws visitors from across the world to its historic campus each year. Trinity accounts for one-fifth of all spin-out companies from Irish higher education institutions, helping to turn Ireland into an innovation-intensive, high-productivity economy. For SPARKS, Science Gallery Dublin hosted the exhibition and activities in January 2018. Science Gallery Dublin is the National Hub for Hypatia, and led Studioblab, which created a European network that provided a platform for creative projects that bridge divisions between science, art and design. Science Gallery Dublin developed three exhibitions as part of the Studioblab project: SURFACE TENSION (2011), HACK THE CITY (2012) and GROW YOUR OWN (2014).

P5-Cite main missions are to improve science and space education for all citizens, to share developments in space and astronomy with the greatest number possible and inspire a desire to learn more. Throughout its different actions and activities, Cité de l'espace is deeply involved in supporting the collaboration between formal and non formal science and space education providers and thus supports an open schooling method.

P6-UC Limburg provides extensive expertise developing pedagogical expertise for teachers. It participates in this project with the Teacher Education Department and its research unit Expertise Centre Art of Teaching. In this project UC Limburg will mainly contribute by providing a large network of schools, coordinating and implementing the activities with schools in Belgium, mentoring the participating groups of students and organizing trainings for teachers. The Centre is also currently involved as a partner in ESERO Belgium, the European Space Education Resource Office which is a collaboration between ESA and national Partners.

P7-OEWF has a significant expertise in the space incubator field and Non-formal and on Informal Science Education Providers and Leaders. Originally a grass root organization for aerospace engineers, scientists and people with a passion for space, it has evolved into a research institution with a focus on astronautics and space research in the past decade, has significantly contributed to the field of lunar and Mars analog research by developing robotic and human spaceflight technologies and gaining operational experience with a focus on Mars exploration. During all its missions, the OeWF invites young students and teenagers to participate in the mission.

P8-NUCLIO is a non-profit association with the main aim of promoting the inclusion of active research as a tool for science learning in schools. NUCLIO has vast expertise on Non-formal and Informal Science Education programmes, being involved in several EC projects aiming to introduce innovative practices for science learning in formal and informal settings (PLATON, OSOS, STORIES, IDiverSE). NUCLIO is also the coordinator of one of the largest astronomy education efforts in the world, the Galileo Teacher Training Program, a legacy of the International Year of Astronomy 2009 that has reached since 2009 over 100 nations and 50 000 teachers.

P9-NOA is the oldest Research Centre in Greece, which includes the Institute for Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications and Remote Sensing. This Institute is the main hub for space research in Greece with an accumulated expertise on Space Sciences that is unique at national level. NOA also has a solid record of nearly 20 years of public outreach and science education programmes. These are coordinated and implemented by the two visitors centres operated by Institute. They offer diverse outreach programmes targeting different audiences and groups and have attracted in the last 5-years more than 200,000 visitors and about 3,000 schools.

P10-UANTWERPEN focuses on cutting – edge basic research underpinning high-quality academic programs at Bachelor, Master, and PhD level. Currently UAAntwerp is involved in 66 projects funded under H2020.

3.4. Resources to be committed

In the following we summarise the staff effort and the allocation of resources for the initiative:

Table 3.4a: Summary of staff effort

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	Total Person-Months per Participant
1-IAU	8	4	2	8	2	2	0	26
2-ULEI	4	14	2	2	2	2	0	26
3-EA	3	5	12	2	2	2	0	26
4-TCD	2	1	1	1	17.5	1	0.5	24
5-CEspace	1	3	5	1	1	1	0	12
6-ULimburg	1	2	4	1	1	1	0	10
7-OEWF	1	3	5	1	1	1	0	12
8-Nuclio	1	3	5	1	1	1	0	12
9 – NOA	1	3	5	1	1	1	0	12
10-UAntwerpen	1	3	2	1	1	1	0	9
Total Person Months	23	41	43	19	29.5	13	0.5	169

Table 3.4b: ‘Other direct cost’ items (travel, equipment, infrastructure, goods and services, large research infrastructure)

P1 – IAU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	27 200	9 500 EUR: 6 European trips (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR). 4 International trips (for OAD and OAO) (Per trip: 700 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR) 15 000 EUR: For travel costs for teams: 3 Challenges(x 2 European Teams x 5 flights (4 students + 1 teacher+1 local partner (e.g.: space company or researcher))x 300 EUR per flight)+(1 Non-European team x 5 flights (4 students + 1 teacher+1 local partner)x 700 EUR per flight) 2 700 EUR: 3 Challenges x 3 European experts x 300 EUR per flight
Equipment	2000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software (250 EUR)
Other goods and services	10 000	5 000 EUR: Dissemination and promotion costs (2000 EUR for video material, 3000 EUR for educational material visual and writing content development); 5000 EUR Logistical costs for local activities, including engagement with schools (1500 EUR Catering costs, 2000 EUR, promotional material, 1500EUR open schooling resources material development).
Total	39 200	

P2 – ULEI	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	4000	4 European trips (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR)
Equipment	2000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software (250 EUR)
Other goods and services	30 000	Mission-Oriented Website development (15 000 EUR), Content development for challenges and advocacy actions (editorial & graphic) (15 000 EUR), 5000 EUR Logistical costs for local activities, including engagement with schools (1500 EUR Catering costs, 2000 EUR, promotional material, 1500EUR open schooling resources material development).
Total	41 000	

P3 – EA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	3000	3 European trips (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR)
Equipment	2000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software (250 EUR)
Other goods and services	55 000	5 000 Logistical costs for local activities, including engagement with schools (1500 EUR Catering costs, 2000 EUR, promotional material, 1500EUR open schooling resources material development). 45 000 EUR: Local costs for the organisation of the 3 Challenge Hackathon in M11 or 12 (per challenge: daily costs/accommodation for 18pax (12 students, 3 teachers, 3 local stakeholders and 3 experts)x175/day x 4 days). 5000 MOOC production costs (video and post-production)
Total	60 000	

P4 – TCD	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	8000	9 European trips: 3 consortium meetings and 5 evaluation observations (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR)
Equipment	4000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software licence fees for evaluation software and statistical analysis (2250 EUR)
Other goods and services	8000	Activities: Costs for evaluation workshops and focus groups to test research instruments and gather feedback (3000 EUR), as well as transcription (2000 EUR) and translation costs (3000 EUR).
Total	20 000	

P5 – CITE	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	5000	5 European trips (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR). Including 2 consortium meetings, 2 conferences and 1 visit to one of the project partners.
Equipment	2000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software (250 EUR)
Other goods and services	8000	Logistical costs for local activities, including engagement with schools (1500 EUR Catering costs, 2000 EUR, promotional material, 1500EUR open schooling resources material development). 3000 EUR for mentorships costs with space industries.
Total	15 000	

P6 – UC LIMBURG	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	3000	3 European trips (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR). Including 2 consortium meetings, 1 conference.
Equipment	2000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software (250 EUR)
Other goods and services	5000	Logistical costs for local activities, including engagement with schools (1500 EUR Catering costs, 2000 EUR, promotional material, 1500EUR open schooling resources material development)
Total	10 000	

P7 – OEWF	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	5000	5 European trips (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR). Including 2 consortium meetings, 2 conferences and 1 visit to one of the project partners.
Equipment	2000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software (250 EUR)
Other goods and services	8000	5000 EUR Logistical costs for local activities, including engagement with schools (1500 EUR Catering costs, 2000 EUR, promotional material, 1500EUR open schooling resources material development). 3000 EUR for AMADEE-20 Mars analog Mission development.
Total	15 000	

P8 – NUCLIO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	3000	3 European trips (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR).
Equipment	2000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software (250 EUR)
Other goods and services	5000	Logistical costs for local activities, including engagement with schools (1500 EUR Catering costs, 2000 EUR, promotional material, 1500EUR open schooling resources material development)
Total	10 000	

P9 – NOA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	3000	3 European trips (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR). Including 2 consortium meetings, 1 conference.
Equipment	2000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software (250 EUR)
Other goods and services	5000	Logistical costs for local activities, including engagement with schools (1500 EUR Catering costs, 2000 EUR, promotional material, 1500EUR open schooling resources material development)
Total	10 000	

P10 – UANTWERPEN	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	3000	3 European trips (Per trip: 300 EUR for Flight, 4 days, with daily costs: 175 EUR). Including 2 consortium meetings, 1 conference.
Equipment	2000	Laptop (1750 EUR), Software (250 EUR)
Other goods and services	5000	Logistical costs for local activities, including engagement with schools (1500 EUR Catering costs, 2000 EUR, promotional material, 1500EUR open schooling resources material development)
Total	10 000	